

DELIVERABLE

Project Number: 964591

Project Acronym: SMART-electron

Project Title: Ultrafast All-Optical Spatio-Temporal
Electron Modulators: Opening New Frontiers In Electron Microscopy

Funding Scheme: H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2020

Number of Work Package	WP6
Number of Deliverable	D6.1
Title of Deliverable	Project logo and webpage (Second release)
Lead Beneficiary	QED
Due Date	M12

Start Date of Project: 01/05/2021

Duration: 48 months

Project Logo and Webpage (Second Release)

D6.1

Version 1.0

Authors:

L.M.C. Giberti (QED)
R. Santucci (QED)

Reviewers:

G.M. Vanacore (UNIMIB)

Project funded by the European Commission within the FET OPEN Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	R. Santucci	QED	First draft
0.2	L.M.C Giberti R.Santucci	QED QED	First complete version
0.3	L.M.C Giberti R.Santucci	QED QED	Second complete version - overall cleanup and insertion of text+images for logo section
0.4	G.M. Vanacore	UNIMIB	Review and comments, minor changes
0.4.9	R. Santucci	QED	Inserted new images and additional web-page texts. Text for website sections reviewed
0.5	L.M.C Giberti R.Santucci	QED QED	Final version integrating the comments of the peer reviewers and partners, Annex 1 created, Annex 2 updated
1.0	L.M.C Giberti	QED	Added a few extra images

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this deliverable lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 THE SMART-electron LOGO	8
1.1 SMART-electron Visual Identity	8
1.2 The SMART-electron Logo	9
2 THE SMART-electron WEBSITE	17
2.1 Functions Of The Project Website	17
2.2 Structure And Layout based on target users	18
2.2.1 Landing page	19
2.2.2 The main navigation bar	21
[SE logo button]	21
Science	22
A layperson's introduction to the science of SMART-electron	22
The main concepts behind SMART-electron	22
Introductory Bibliography	23
NEW Research Papers	23
People	23
UPDATE Project Staff	23
NEW Meet your scientist	24
NEW Women in science	24
NEW New hires	24
EU Funded	25
Events	25
NEW 2021 International Conference	25
NEW 2021 FIM-S3 Seminar	25
NEW 2021 Wiki Science Competition	26
NEW 2021 Researchers' Night	26
NEW 2022 Nano Colloquia Seminar	26
NEW 2022 Wikipedia Edit-a-thon	26
UPDATE News	27
UPDATE Press	27
Contacts	28
3 TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	29
4 SERVICES AND OTHER WEBPAGES	29
4.1 SOCIAL NETWORK INTEGRATION	29

4.2 WEBSITE STATISTICS	30
4.3 FURTHER WORK ON DATA GATHERING AFTER SECOND WEBSITE RELEASE	30
5 THE CONTENT	30
5.1 EDITORIAL TEAM	30
6 CONCLUSION	32
ANNEX 1: WEBSITE SCREENSHOTS	33
DESKTOP VERSION	33
MOBILE VERSION	39
ANNEX 2: LIST OF THE PAGES IN THE SECOND RELEASE OF THE SMART-electron WEBSITE	44
About the project	44
Who we are	44
What we do	47
Project Structure (with WPs)	48
People	48
Project Team	48
Meet your scientist	57
Shai Tsesses	57
Women in science	58
Luisa Fiandra, Milano Bicocca University	58
Veronica Leccese	60
Science	61
A layperson's introduction to SE	62
The main concepts behind SE	62
Introductory bibliography	64
Research papers	67
EU Funded	68
Events	68
2022 Nano Colloquia: Artificial neural network for automatic alignment of electron optical devices	68
2022 SMART-electron Wikipedia Edit-a-thon	69
2021 International Conference	70
2021 CNR-NANO: FIM-S3 Seminar	71
2021 Smart-Electron Prizes at the Wiki Science Competition	72
SMART-electron, Q-SORT, MINEON and MAX at the Researcher's Night 2021	72
Press room & downloads	73
Contacts	73
News	74
Radio interview at SMART-CITY on Radio 24	74

A new EU-funded H2020 project promises to revolutionize electron microscopy	74
FIM3- Seminar	74
Super scientists invited to nano innovation 2021 forum	74
Nano Colloquia 2022: Artificial neural network for automatic alignment of electron optical devices	74
SMART-electron Wikipedia Edit-a-thon 2022	74
The Smart-Electron Prizes at the Wiki Science Competition 2021	74
SMART-electron at the Researchers' Night 2021	74
ANNEX 3: ABBREVIATIONS	75
Short Name Of Participants	75
List Of Abbreviations	75

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a summary of the work on the SMART-electron project logo and the SMART-electron website, its sections, its technical infrastructures, and its related services in its second release.

This deliverable complies with the SMART-electron DoA outlined in Work Package 6 - Coordination, Management and Dissemination.

It particularly satisfies specifications outlined in Task 6.3, Dissemination and Communication activities, thus providing a reference point for all necessary actions regarding the promotion of SMART-electron's Web presence.

The promotional elements addressed in the document are the design and definition of the SMART-electron logo and the related graphic elements & rules which determine the website graphics and layout.

The current document is comprised of 6 Chapters, an Executive Summary, Conclusions and an Annex.

The first Chapter describes the SMART-electron branding and visual identity strategies, which notably includes a paragraph devoted to the description of the SMART-electron logo.

Chapter 2, 3, 4 present respectively an overview of SMART-electron's website layout and structure, its technical infrastructure and the tools it offers, its integration and interactions with Social Networks and additional services (e.g., web feeds, analysis tools, etc.).

Chapter 5 describes the workflow of the editorial team and the content of the website's various sections.

1 THE SMART-ELECTRON LOGO

1.1 SMART-ELECTRON VISUAL IDENTITY

The study of a visual identity for SMART-electron began right at the project inception. Due to the specialist nature of the subject matter, it is challenging to devise a set of graphic objects and rules that are both meaningful and striking.

Because we are convinced that a careful dissemination of the project's results will be of great value not only to academic but also to lay circles, a vigorous push towards engagement with non-specialised audiences has been a guiding principle in our work since the beginning. We feel that a low standard of design and copywriting has in the past been the cause of (otherwise-excellent) science projects' limited success in attracting a general audience. Luckily, thanks also to the efforts of the European Commission, the situation has evolved quickly in recent years: there is a growing investment in communication, branding, and public relations aimed towards a wider audience.

In keeping pace with these positive outreach initiatives, we believe that SMART-electron's branding approach should be driven principally by an emphasis on the following strengths: 1) the beauty and richness of meaning of the concepts that the project entails; 2) the scientific excellence of its endeavour and of the participating institutions; 3) the beauty of the imagery generated by the research work pertaining to the project.

In accordance with the parameters of our DoA, a professionally-conducted study of SMART-electron's visual identity and branding was undertaken. We are confident that this investment will bring added value to the project and distinctive advantages to the consortium. At the core of our efforts is the intention of developing an overall 'look-and-feel', a unique and easily identifiable personality to be consistently declined across all platforms used during dissemination. This undertaking includes the following branding elements:

1. Basic Elements

- i. *Brand logo*, i.e. the symbol through which the project is easily recognised, in both print and electronic media, and notably in thumbnails pertaining to social media profiles and browser favicons.
- ii. *Branding architecture*, that is a coherent system of typographical rules, visual relations, and hierarchies between the brand-logo and the (typo)graphical elements connectable to it (e.g. the SMART-electron brand-logo and event titles).

2. Web

- i. Templates for the web pages that are compatible with WordPress and the CMS of the website. In particular, these include: a. main website page; b. general page template, e.g. About the project; c. news & events pages template; e. contacts page template, etc.

A vast selection of graphs, illustrations, as well as TEM images and motifs was assembled for the visual identity study. Graphic artists were also briefed qualitatively on various aspects of the science behind the project and of the challenges involved in the project activities. The first element arising from the visual identity study was the design of the SMART-electron logo.

1.2 THE SMART-ELECTRON LOGO

As the first graphic element to be designed for the project, the logo can be thought of as the cornerstone upon which everything else will be built in terms of graphics and overall outreach & dissemination.

The logo has to concurrently fulfil several functions, as it should be: instantly recognisable, elegant, representative of the project, simple, easy to reproduce at various different sizes and on many different media. Ideally, it should also have evocative qualities.

In designing it, it was our intention from the outset to seek to provide a graphic analogue of some of the concepts and/or experimental procedures that are characteristic of the project. Given the project's central concept, we explored and evolved several ideas that could represent various forms of interaction or relationship between an electron and a photon. In particular, it seemed natural to try to symbolise the wave-particle duality through two distinct elements, characterised by curved and straight lines respectively. Another line of enquiry explored the forms that can be generated by some of the equations at the heart of SMART-electron. The starting point was a series of exploratory renderings by the creative director, Luca Giberti:

Figure 1. Some early concepts

Various ideas were explored, with examples of applications to study how the different possible logos would influence their respective 'graphic offsprings', i.e. the other graphic assets that would follow, such as motifs, or tote bags, brochures, vinyl banners, etc. (see figures). As it is customary at QED, the designs were evolved by selection but also through a form of 'horizontal gene transfer', i.e. by sometimes grafting features or colours from one design to another.

Figure 2. One of the alternatives explored for the logo, with ensuing possible motifs and graphic assets

For instance, the sinusoidal or wave-like motif was in turn developed and exploited to build stylised representations of equipotential lines around the atoms in a crystal lattice:

Figure 3. Another alternative that was developed for the logo, with ensuing possible motifs and graphic assets

Throughout the design phase, we followed QED's customary guiding principles of clarity and simplicity, which notably entail the adoption of a minimalistic tonal and chromatic palette, as well as checking that the design works first and foremost in monochrome. In particular, two alternative palettes were considered, both avoiding the use of primary colours:

Figure 4. The two alternative palettes taken into consideration

Another guiding principle has been the suitability of the design to be animated as part of a possible ident which we are thinking of splicing in at the beginning or at the end of any SMART-electron video asset.

We had to take into account the use of the logo within the intended website design, and also within the intended designs for other future SMART-electron graphic assets -such as brochures, posters, vinyl banners, possibly a handout gadget, etc.-, which will be specified in D6.2 - Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan. This meant, *inter alia*, clearly differentiating between the project logo and the textures of the website images - for example those arising from complex physics. Other constraints we had to keep in mind were

1. the reproduction of the logo in printed form (=offset print done from CMYK files), which sets constraints on the useable RGB gamut;
2. the reproduction of the logo as a thumbnail in social media and as a favicon in browsers, which imply the elimination or strong aliasing of fine details.

After several generations, we finally settled on the idea of the separate stylised initials ('incomplete initials' version), which lends itself well to interesting and striking textures obtained through deceptively simple repetitions:

Figure 5. Study of the 'incomplete initials' version of the logo, with possible ensuing motifs

The final version was the result of several experiments with non-primary colours from the second palette:

Figure 6. The SMART-electron logo in its final iteration

The final logo design lends itself well to the reduction to favicon:

Figure 7. The SMART-electron logo in its two favicon versions for social media and the Web

Crucially, this version also works well as a fertile starting point for all designs, as it can be seen from the following mock-ups:

Figure 8. Mock-ups of possible future designs based on the SMART-electron logo

Figure 9. Mock-ups of possible future designs based on the SMART-electron logo

In the final logo, the S represents the wave aspect and the E the particle aspect of the quantum description. But equally, just like in Feynman's diagrams, the curvy S could be taken to symbolise the photon and the straight E to symbolise the electron.

The deliberate incompleteness of these two graphic signs can be interpreted as representative of the inference processes that are necessary to form the full physical picture of a certain system based on a set of sparse or at any rate discrete observations. But equally, the incompleteness could represent the impossibility of a completely deterministic description of the system, describing all of its "elements of reality" -as Einstein called them- under the rules of quantum mechanics.

Also with view to future animation and further graphic design work, we experimented with alternative colour schemes for the logo. In the end, we settled on three, depending on the intended application: the standard version in lime green, but also a black and a white version (see figure). Each version is available as an isolated logotype or as logotype + title.

The logo was well received and garnered the praise of several partners.

2 THE SMART-ELECTRON WEBSITE

The following domain has been registered for the project website:

<http://www.smartelectron.eu/>

The website is the reference point of the project's communication and dissemination strategy, as well as a tool for work for the partners.

Figure 10. Logic view of the first release of SMART-electron website; downloadable files are represented by rectangles

2.1 FUNCTIONS OF THE PROJECT WEBSITE

The SMART-electron website is the first port of call for anyone wanting to know more about the project. At the same time, it is also SMART-electron's own visiting card, so to speak.

Other important features of the website are:

- its usefulness for journalists and media people, who can download press kits and photos;
- its educational function, thanks to pages devoted to selected bibliography and common-language explanations;
- further to this, its operational function as an online point-of-access to all of the project's Open Access output: research papers, documents, open data;
- its blog/news feature, which acts as the very first publishing outlet for news about SMART-electron, which will then be re-posted to social media.

Due to this multitude of needs, the website was conceived and designed based on criteria of clarity, functionality, simplicity, and beauty. Everything is intended to drive the user's attention towards the main

function of the website: to provide information about the SMART-electron project, its activities, progress, and achievements.

Since the Internet has become a mostly mobile medium, the website was conceived from the outset to be smartphone- and tablet-compatible. That is why we adopted a responsive web design solution, i.e. “...a Web design approach aimed at crafting sites to provide an optimal viewing experience – easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling - across a wide range of devices (from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones)” (Wikipedia). Having said so, given its intended target audiences (which comprise science buffs and schools, other fellow scientists, and journalists - see next chapter), the main scenario of use of SMART-electron’s website is via desktop browser.

The SMART-electron website is W3C compliant.

Figure 11. The SMART-electron website is conceived for both desktop and mobile use

2.2 STRUCTURE AND LAYOUT BASED ON TARGET USERS

The website structure and the design of its graphical user interface were conceived bearing in mind the main scenarios of use and the resulting ‘user trajectories’ from the moment users land on the home page until they reach the information they seek. Model readers thus considered include the following three macro categories: users interested in knowing more about the project (including schools), scientists managers and admins working in scientific research, journalists.

For the latter two groups, the logical layout of the main navigation bar (see below) and the shallow nature of the page tree (Figure 10) result in the fastest possible path from landing on the home page to retrieving the desired information.

On the other hand, users who are just generally curious are invited to dwell on the rich, high-resolution scientific imagery on which the design is based. Striking visuals are one of the key features of the SMART-electron website and of the SMART-electron communication strategy in general. They are the easiest way to begin communicating and generating interest in complex information, not only amongst professionals but also, crucially, within the general public. Besides this, all modern media channels -including social media such as Instagram, Facebook, but also messaging platforms such as Whatsapp, Signal, Snapchat- are mostly or even exclusively image-centric.

A limited colour palette of black, white, and lime was employed throughout. This is due to several reasons: primarily, to make the website stand out in the hyper-crowded and multicoloured landscape of the Web; but

also, in order to make the few colour elements within it stand out, which is especially useful for highlighting items of great importance - such as the EU flag.

As a deliberate choice, the website eschews animations in favour of moveable slides revealing significant images taken from the research papers leading to SMART-electron. This choice confers an active role to the user.

The website structure and content will evolve in time according to the needs of the project and of its partners.

2.2.1 Landing page

The landing (home) page of the website is a clean-looking and intuitive access point from which all further navigation ensues.

It features large backgrounds derived from papers that laid the foundations of SMART-electron's work. In the upper portion of the landing page is the main navigation bar. At the bottom of the page the user will find the EU flag and the "This project is funded by the EU" caption.

Figure 12. SMART-electron home page

Figure 13. SMART-electron home page

Figure 14. SMART-electron home page

2.2.2 The main navigation bar

The horizontal navigation bar features the following links (NB: the texts for each of the following subpages are given in Annex 1):

[SE logo button]

A button for getting back to the home page, which immediately provides all the essential information about the project, featuring the following paragraphs:

Who we are

A brief description of the SMART-electron Partners, with links to their respective websites.

What we do

A summary of the overall mission and activities past and future of the project, which will be updated as SMART-electron progresses.

Project structure

A graph summarising the work package structure and dependencies of the Project.

Figure 15. SMART-electron home page

Science

The Science section provides a concise description of the scientific background of the project, with links to further reading. At present it features three sub-pages. A further sub-page devoted to the publications generated by the project will be added in the second release. The three current sub-pages are:

- **A layperson's introduction to the science of SMART-electron**

It provides a short explanation of the project in simple terms, with engaging language.

Figure 16. SMART-electron - Science section, sub-page devoted to an introduction to SMART-electron for the layperson

- **The main concepts behind SMART-electron**

This section provides a short glossary-like introduction, with links, to some of the most important concepts underlying SMART-electron's activities.

- **Introductory Bibliography**

An introductory scientific bibliography to published research papers on the science behind SMART-electron.

Figure 17. SMART-electron - Science section, sub-page devoted to an introductory bibliography of the project

- ***NEW* Research Papers**

A new “Research Papers” page, listing all of SMART-electron research papers, was created in the “Science” section, for better Open Access useability and compliance. Each paper entry links to the corresponding PDF file on ARXIV, for direct download.

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/smart-electron-research-papers/>

People

- ***UPDATE* Project Staff**

The Project Staff page was set up in order to offer details of the project staff (photos, bios, recently-completed projects). It features the Principal Investigators' and team leaders bios .

Figure 18. SMART-electron People page

- ***NEW* Meet your scientist**

A “Meet Your Scientist” section was created, and updated throughout the first year of the project, featuring written interviews to the SMART-electron scientists.

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/meet-your-scientist-2/>

- ***NEW* Women in science**

A new “Women In Science” series, featuring two interviews with women scientists, was placed in the People section and menu.

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/women-in-science/>

- ***NEW* New hires**

A “New hires” page was created featuring short bios and pics of the newly hired members of the project team.

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/new-hires/>

EU Funded

A brief introduction to the EC and EC projects, with special emphasis on EIC.

Figure 19. SMART-electron EU Funded page

Events

This section features future events organised by SMART-electron, such as the SMART-electron International Conferences.

- ***NEW* 2021 International Conference**

A page with the announcement of the 2021 SMART-electron 2021 Conference was created:

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/events-smart-electron/>

- ***NEW* 2021 FIM-S3 Seminar**

A page with the description of the FIM-S3 Seminar held by Prof Giovanni Maria Vanacore was created:

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/cnr-nano-fim-s3-seminar/>

- ***NEW* 2021 Wiki Science Competition**

The Wiki Science Competition (WSC) is an international photo contest for the sciences. It is organised by Wikimedia, that is the movement behind [Wikipedia](#), the free encyclopaedia – a global collaboration authored by volunteers. SMART-electron issued a special prize for this competition and the related webpage was created:

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/the-smart-electron-prizes-at-the-wiki-science-competition-2021/>

- ***NEW* 2021 Researchers' Night**

The European Researchers' Night is a Europe-wide public event, which displays the diversity of science and its impact on citizens' daily lives in fun, inspiring ways. A page dedicated to this event co-organised by SMART- electron was created:

- ***NEW* 2022 Nano Colloquia Seminar**

A page devoted to the Seminar Nano Colloquia 2022: Artificial neural network for automatic alignment of electron optical devices was created:

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/nano-colloquia-2022-artificial-neural-network-for-automatic-alignment-of-electron-optical-devices/>

- ***NEW* 2022 Wikipedia Edit-a-thon**

The SMART-electron 2022 Wikipedia Edit-a-thon was organised by QED in collaboration with [Wikimedia Italia](#). The goal of this event was to edit and update Wikipedia articles on concepts related to the theme of the conference, including electron vortex beams, the double slit experiment with electrons, and synthetic holography, where information gaps currently exist. Scientists, researchers, and Ph.D. students participated in the research.

A new page regarding this event was created:

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/smart-electron-wikipedia-edit-a-thon-2022/>

***UPDATE* News**

The News page is both simple and striking, providing a strong image-based choice of items, each of which can be clicked for further information. This section has been enriched during the first year of the projects will be further enriched in the future.

Figure 20. SMART-electron - News page

It provides news about the project in a standard, easy-to-read format. It is strongly connected with the social networking environment (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram), i.e. News items are also posted in SMART-electron's social media channels, and, conversely, links to follow SMART-electron's social media profiles are provided. This is a critical step towards successful dissemination and community engagement in this technological age. As far as possible, images will be employed to communicate each entry.

This section will feature news and events that are relevant for the SMART-electron community, including diary-like updates about SMART-electron progress, notices of events organised by SMART-electron, of events organised by other institutions, of projects that have invited SMART-electron partners to promote the its activities, and of other events of interest for the SMART-electron community and target users.

***UPDATE* Press**

This section features useful material for journalists and media people such as the partners' press offices. The latest SMART-electron press release, project photos, and the SMART-electron logo can be downloaded directly through the following three links:

Download the latest press release

Download press photos

Download the SMART-electron logo

****NEW* Graphic design standard manual & Package***

****NEW* Poster / Rollup / Brochure / Tote-bag***

Photos come packaged as a single zip file, as do various versions of the logo intended for different uses.

Further promotional material such as brochures, posters, etc. will be added as the project progresses, for download and use by partners in dissemination/outreach events. There will also be an outreach kit that can be used by the project partners as well as by external users in order to produce customised promotional posts.

Links to the SMART-electron social channels are also featured.

Contacts

An easy-to-read access point for communicating with the SMART-electron team.

3 TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The Content Management System that has been selected as the base technology for the SMART-electron website is WordPress¹ - a free, open-source blog tool and publishing platform licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL). WordPress is powered by PHP and MySQL and can easily be customised into a Content Management System (CMS). It has been selected as the base technology for the implementation of the SMART-electron website because of its flexibility, its user-friendly setup and usage, and its provision of a high level of personalisation. Moreover, its widespread availability has spawned a rich ecosystem of plug-ins, which allow users and developers to extend its functionality beyond the features that come with the base installation. This ensemble of qualities makes WordPress the ideal facilitator of a versatile CMS. Moreover, since it is available for free, it represents maximum value for money.

WordPress has a web template system that uses a template processor. The processor makes it easy to re-arrange widgets and install and switch between themes. The PHP and HTML code used by the themes can also be edited for more advanced customisations.

WordPress has a number of useful features, which include integrated link management, a search-engine-friendly, clean permalink structure; the ability to assign nested, multiple categories for articles; support for tagging of posts and articles. Automatic filters are also included, providing standardised formatting and styling of text within articles.

Multimedia files such as images, videos, flash movies, image galleries, slideshows, etc. can be uploaded and linked to (or displayed in) pages and articles, or embedded directly from other places (e.g. YouTube).

WordPress provides several ready-to-use options for the display of website archives. They can be arranged according to year, month, week, day, category, or author. New archives can be created and easily linked. Since WordPress generates pages dynamically, all these archive pages come at no additional space-cost to the server.

WordPress' built-in search functionality allows visitors to the website to search for terms they are interested in; the search terms are highlighted, making it even easier for them to find what they were looking for.

WordPress supports the Trackback² and Pingback³ standards for displaying links to other sites that have themselves been linked to a post or article.

Hosting was arranged externally, using value-for-money criteria and a tried-and-trusted provider.

4 SERVICES AND OTHER WEBPAGES

4.1 SOCIAL NETWORK INTEGRATION

The SMART-electron website allows for easy, one-click sharing, bookmarking, and emailing of articles and pages through the provision of a large variety of services.

In particular, AddThis is the add-on tool intended to make sharing and bookmarking simple, and to place at the immediate disposition of users all of the leading web 2.0 social networking, bookmarking, blogging, and email services⁴. Once added, visitors to the website can bookmark an item using through services such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and many more. SMART-electron Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram pages will be created in order to engage a wider public made up of both professionals and nonprofessionals.

¹ www.wordpress.org

² www.sixapart.com/pronet/docs/trackback_spec

³ www.hixie.ch/specs/pingback/pingback

⁴ The code is available at www.addthis.com/

The updating of the Facebook page is done either automatically or manually by the authorised managers; automatic updating is based on feeds taken from the SMART-electron website and the posting of news and select memes of interest to the SMART-electron target audience. Authorised managers can manually post information about events or other relevant information related to the project or partners, as well as select content proposed by the partners. QED is responsible for managing the social network pages.

4.2 WEBSITE STATISTICS

Website usage is monitored through Google Analytics, a very popular Web analytics solution that provides many insights into one's website traffic and marketing effectiveness. It allows for Advanced Segmentation, Custom Reports, Advanced Analysis Tools, Analytics Intelligence, Custom Variables, and Data exports⁵.

Google Analytics can track visitors from all referrers, including search engines, display advertising, pay-per-click networks, email marketing, and digital 'collateral' such as links within PDF documents.

The service offers the following specific statistical insights:

- number of visits and number of unique visitors
- visit duration and last visits
- domains/countries of visitors
- host list, last visits and unresolved IP addresses list, most viewed, entry and exit pages
- browsers used
- robot visits
- search engines, keyphrases and keywords used to arrive at site

Statistics are managed by the webmaster; they are analysed on a tri-monthly basis in order to verify trends and variations.

4.3 FURTHER WORK ON DATA GATHERING AFTER SECOND WEBSITE RELEASE

In order to gain more insights into user behaviour, one script was added to the SMART-electron website code:

1. *NEW* Facebook Pixel in order to provide more insight on user behaviour besides Google Analytics, and better integration with Facebook. This is especially useful given the usefulness of Facebook as a tool for outreach.

We plan to add the following script as well:

2. The free version of Hotjar will also be installed (www.hotjar.com) in order to better characterise the effectiveness of the graphical user interface (GUI) of the Website.

Insights provided by these two tools will be discussed in the future, so as to allow for sufficiently meaningful amounts of data to accumulate.

⁵ For individual features, see <https://marketingplatform.google.com/about/>

5 THE CONTENT

5.1 EDITORIAL TEAM

The **Editorial Team** is comprised of the following members:

- the Communication and Dissemination Manager (Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti, QED) and the Project Coordinator (Dr. Giovanni Maria Vanacore, UNIMIBD) are in charge of deciding overall strategy and monitoring the activities;
- the Communication and Dissemination Executive (Dr. Raffaella Santucci, QED) is in charge of producing, proofreading, checking, and validating the content and publishing the content on the website.

The content to be published on the website is provided by all partners; contributions can be sent to the editorial team.

An **Editorial Board** for the website has been established for quality control of the texts of the website through an internal call for participation. Editors in Chief of the Board are Giovanni Maria Vanacore and Luca Marco Carlo Giberti. The texts to be published on the website will be first shared and agreed upon between the members of the Board. In the event of dispute, a simple one-vote-per-partner, with majority voting, can be used for decision making. In a tied situation, the Editors in Chief have the casting vote.

Other content posted only on social media, such as individual images or shared links to other online resources, will be emailed *ex post* to the members of the Editorial Board.

5.2 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The SMART-electron Project is the sole responsible party for content published on the website; it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission.

The text of the SMART-electron web pages is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 (by) license⁶. This means that users are free to share (copy, distribute, and transmit), remix (adapt), and make commercial use of the website's editorial content under the following conditions:

- **Attribution** — Work must be attributed in the manner specified by the author or licensor (but not in any way that suggests that they endorse you or your use of the work)

It must be noted, however, that the rights to images and videos published on the website are dependent upon the respective attributions of each content provider and may not fall under the above CC licence. Each image has a specific caption with all relevant information.

All other specific contents may be licensed differently according to agreements with single authors.

⁶ <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable describes the work carried out to define the Project's Logo and to implement the second release of the Project's Website.

It has to be noted that the current release of this deliverable presents the second stage in the development of the Website. The website will be continuously and timely updated along the Project's lifetime, and its structure may change to take into account new requirements.

For the duration of the Project's life, the editorial team will continue to:

- constantly update the content of the website
- publish news and events in a timely fashion
- make project deliverables and other documentation available in a timely fashion.

ANNEX 1: WEBSITE SCREENSHOTS

DESKTOP VERSION

SMART-electron
Deliverable D6.1
Project Logo and Webpage (Second Release)

SMART-electron
Deliverable D6.1
Project Logo and Webpage (Second Release)

MOBILE VERSION

SMART-electron
Deliverable D6.1
Project Logo and Webpage (Second Release)

SMART-electron
Deliverable D6.1
Project Logo and Webpage (Second Release)

ANNEX 2: LIST OF THE PAGES IN THE SECOND RELEASE OF THE SMART-ELECTRON WEBSITE

SMART-electron [=landing page]

About

Who we are

What we do

Science

A layperson's introduction to SMART-electron research

Introductory bibliography

People

EU Funded

Events

Press & Downloads

Contacts

Reserved area

ABOUT THE PROJECT

SMART-electron aims at developing an innovative technological platform for designing, realizing and operating all-optical rapidly-programmable phase masks for electrons. SMART-electron will introduce a new paradigm where properly synthesized ultrafast electromagnetic fields will be used for engineering the phase space of a free-electron wave function.

This will allow us to achieve unprecedented space/time/energy/momentum shaping of electron matter waves, thus surpassing conventional passive monolithic schemes and revolutionizing the way materials are investigated in electron microscopy.

WHO WE ARE

1 - University of Milano-Bicocca – UNIMIB

The University of Milano-Bicocca is a young university (established in 1998) with a strong commitment to international research in science, medicine and social sciences. It is one of the most dynamic and research- and innovation-oriented Italian universities. In recent years, it has created an extensive network including many well-established universities, research centres and top corporations. In terms of projects, UNIMIB is currently involved in more than 100 ongoing European granted projects (within the H2020 programme, COST Actions, Justice, EIT-KIC Raw Materials among others); for 26 of those, UNIMIB acts also as the coordinator. Just to mention the H2020-MSCA program, UNIMIB is coordinator of 7 MSCA-ITN, 2 MSCA-RISE, 2 MSCA-NIGHT, 5 MSCA-IF and it is beneficiary of 9 additional MSCA-ITN and 2

MSCA-RISE. Furthermore, UNIMIB hosts 11 ERC projects: 4 starting grant, 5 consolidator grants, 1 proof of concept and 1 synergy grant. UNIMIB is also the beneficiary of 3 FET-Open grants. The research groups involved in this project are based at the Department of Materials Science (UNIMIB-Mater) and at the Department of Biotechnology and Bioscience (UNIMIB-Bio). Both departments have recently received from the Ministry of Education and Research the qualification of *Department of Excellence*, which is given to only 180 departments across all disciplines within the entire country (top 10% or better). Moreover, they are both routinely ranked at the top positions among all medium-sized departments in their related areas from the National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes.

École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne – EPFL

The École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) is a research institute and university in Lausanne, Switzerland, specializing in the natural sciences and engineering. It currently ranks 18th in the world according to the QS university rankings. According to The Times Higher Education, EPFL ranks 2nd of the world top 100 universities under 50 years old in 2019. Currently, the EPFL hosts over 11000 students. The EPFL is located in the French Switzerland, and is the twin of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETHZ). As part of its research and teaching activities, EPFL is one of the only universities to run a nuclear reactor, a fusion reactor, a Gene/Q Supercomputer, and have P3 bio-hazard facilities. The EPFL is among the most diverse institutions in the world with students from 112 different nationalities. The activities of the current project will be carried out at the Laboratory for Ultrafast Microscopy and Electron Scattering (LUMES), directed by Prof. Carbone, which focuses on the investigation of matter in out-of-equilibrium conditions by means of electron spectroscopy, diffraction and imaging.

Main tasks in the project

The LUMES team will be in charge, together with the teams at UNIMIB and ICFO, of modelling, designing and characterizing the photonic-based free-electron modulators (PELMs) according to the tasks described in WP1. The LUMES team, together with UNIMIB and TECHNION, will participate in the design and realization of the modified section of the TEM column, as detailed in WP2. LUMES will be in charge of implementing the Ramsey-type Holographic Imaging (RHI) method and in developing its practical applications on strongly-correlated materials according to the tasks described in WP3.

3 – The Institute of Photonic Science – ICFO

The Institute of Photonic Sciences (www.icfo.eu) was founded in 2002 by the Government of Catalonia and the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. Located in the Mediterranean Technology Park in the metropolitan area of Barcelona, the institute currently hosts 400 people, organized in 26 research groups in 60 state-of-the-art research laboratories. In addition to two consecutive accreditations of the Severo Ochoa national program for research excellence, ICFOians have been awarded 15 elite ICREA Professorships and 32 European Research Council grants. ICFO participates actively in the European Technological Platform Photonics21 and is very proactive in fostering entrepreneurial activities, spin-off creation, and creating collaborations and links between industry and ICFO researchers. To date, ICFO has helped create 7 start-up companies.

ICFO will exploit the competences of the Nanophotonics Theory group, which has developed theory, analytical techniques and advanced computational codes for the description of electron beams in their interactions with nanophotonic structures, as well as for studying the control of electron beams by means of interaction with photonic structures. These knowledge and accumulated set of techniques will be applied with full power to the present project.

Main tasks in the project

The ICFO team will be in charge, together with the teams at UNIMIB and EPFL, of theoretically modelling and designing the photonic-based free-electron modulators according to the tasks described in WP1. In particular the ICFO team will be in charge of delivering the user-friendly computer code for full phase mask design. ICFO will also actively participate in implementing the deep-learning algorithm for real-time SLM control based on the detected electron phase profile. The ICFO team will also theoretically support the

teams at UNIMIB, EPFL and TECHNION in the implementation of the RHI, ESPI and Quantum-CL methods, respectively.

4 – Israel Institute of Technology – TECHNION

Founded in 1912, Technion – Israel Institute of Technology is Israel's first university and its largest center of applied research. Technion is ranked among the leading technological universities worldwide. A major source of the innovation and brainpower that drives the Israeli economy, Technion is the engine behind Israel's renown as the iconic "Startup Nation". Technion people, ideas, and inventions have made, and continue to make tremendous scientific contributions in fields such as medicine, sustainable energy, computer science, water conservation, photonics and nanotechnology. It is one of a handful of technological institutes worldwide with a medical school, facilitating the rapid development of advanced therapies and devices, from the laboratory to the patient's bedside. Technion's success is attributed to its unwavering commitment to excellence in education and research. The University is proud of its four Nobel laureates – Aaron Ciechanover, Avram Hershko, Dan Shechtman, and Arieh Warshel. Technion currently ties with MIT in the 8th place for the number of Nobel prize winners this century. Technion offers degrees in all fields of science and engineering, architecture and town planning, medicine, industrial management, education, and environmental studies. It houses 18 faculties, 60 research centers and institutes, and 10 interdisciplinary research frameworks. Since Albert Einstein founded the first Technion Society in Germany in 1923, Technion's worldwide network of friends has expanded worldwide to encompass 21 countries. Technion International, home to the university's global academic community, offers dedicated degree programs in English to international students. The university has academic agreements with more than 200 universities and research authorities around the globe. The activities of the current project will be carried out at the AdQuanta Group headed by Prof. Ido Kaminer, which focuses on: i) fundamentals of light-matter interactions with novel nanophotonics; ii) radiation generation in spectral ranges inaccessible by existing technology; iii) probing topological phenomena in new materials with ultrafast electrons and photons.

Main tasks in the project

The TECHNION team will support the teams at EPFL, ICFO and UNIMIB in the modelling, designing and characterization of the photonic-based free-electron modulators according to the tasks described in WP1. The TECHNION team will also actively participate, together with UNIMIB and EPFL, in the design and realization of the modified section of the TEM column as detailed in WP2. TECHNION will be in charge of implementing the Quantum Cathodoluminescence (Quantum-CL) method and in developing its practical applications according to the tasks described in WP5.

5 – Italian National Research Council – CNR

Istituto di Nanoscienze (NANO) is dedicated to frontier research in nanoscience and nanotechnology, established in 2010. Its S3-laboratory in Modena is devoted to "nanoStructures and bioSystems at Surfaces", and is based on a multidisciplinary approach and close interaction between experimental and theoretical activities. The group of quantum electron optics and microscopy in NANO has a long standing experience and a world leadership in theoretical and experimental static electron beam shaping, vortex beam and electron-matter interaction. The group is also active on electron simulation and computer aided microscopy and is working now on artificial intelligence and deep learning applications in microscopy.

Main tasks in the project

The CNR team will be in charge of the optimization and implementation of the work flow for the microfabrication of the electron-transparent plates according to the task defined in WP1. Moreover, the CNR team will also provide analytical support for the modelling and design of the photonic-based free-electron modulators. The CNR team will be also in charge of developing the deep-learning algorithm for real-time control of SLM as defined in WP2. The CNR team will also actively participate, together with UNIMIB, in the implementation of a compressive-sensing algorithm within the Electron Single-Pixel Imaging (ESPI) method as described in WP4.

6 – HOLOEYE Photonics AG – HOLOEYE

Founded 1999, HOLOEYE Photonics AG is providing products and services in the fields of diffractive optics (DOE), spatial light modulators (SLM) and LCOS microdisplay components. HOLOEYE's development and engineering team is based in Berlin together with technical sales. HOLOEYE offers a great variety of microdisplay based Spatial Light Modulators products for phase and/or amplitude modulation. Based on either translucent or reflective liquid crystal microdisplays, HOLOEYE's SLMs have been utilized in numerous applications ranging over holographic projection and security systems via optical metrology, optical switching devices, biophotonics, laser pulse shaping, and even laser material processing. HOLOEYE developed and characterized a number of phase modulator products for high resolution holographic applications for the visible, near-infrared and telecommunication waveband. The LCOS microdisplay division is providing manufacturers in the field of technical optics, specifically technical projection, imaging, and display technologies, with LCOS microdisplay-hardware other Liquid Crystal micro displays and electronics design services as component solutions. HOLOEYE is specialized in the development of custom drive electronics, flex cables and display packages and also offers custom LC designs and display customizations for specific applications which have demands beyond standard projection displays. HOLOEYE is also providing customized design, fabrication and replication services of Diffractive Optical Elements. Besides that HOLOEYE also offers a broad range of standard Diffractive Optical Elements with various patterns like dot arrays, dot-circles, circles, multi-lines and cross patterns.

Main tasks in the project

HOLOEYE will be in charge of implementing the hardware and software integration of the SLM displays within the experimental setups at UNIMIB, EPFL and TECHNION. In particular, the SLM display will need to be electronically synchronized with the laser and electron detector of the UTEM setup for specific temporal driving via the SLM's driver PC. Moreover, SLM software features will need to be developed for specific integration within the adopted numerical environment and remote control from the deep-learning algorithm.

7 – QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. – QED

QED is a SME devoted to producing films, graphic design, video, new media, theatre. It builds on president and founder Luca Giberti's past 22+ years experience in creative directing for theatre, cinema, social and institutional communication, public understanding of science.

Main Tasks in the project

Partner responsible for production of all graphic assets for Dissemination, Communication and Engagement for the project, including website, graphic identity, graphic design, Dissemination, Communication and Engagement strategy and initiatives. Main responsible for upkeep of Web & social media presence. Partner responsible for events in coordination with Wikimedia Foundation, European Researchers Night, Pint of Science.

WHAT WE DO

SMART-electron aims to develop an innovative technological platform for designing, realising and operating all-optical rapidly-programmable phase masks for electrons. SMART-electron will introduce a new paradigm where properly synthesised ultrafast electromagnetic fields will be used for engineering the phase space of a free-electron wave function. This will allow us to achieve unprecedented space/time/energy/momentum shaping of electron matter waves, thus surpassing conventional passive monolithic schemes and revolutionising the way materials are investigated in electron microscopy.

PROJECT STRUCTURE (WITH WPs)

PEOPLE

Project Team

Dr. Giovanni Maria Vanacore (male, born 27-11-1983). Dr. Vanacore received his B.Sc. (July 2005) and M.Sc. (Dec. 2007) in Physics Engineering from the Politecnico di Milano (Milano, Italy), with a major in condensed matter physics, nanotechnology and lasers. He also received a M.Sc. in Mathematics Engineering (Feb. 2008) from the Politecnico di Torino (Turin, Italy) and a Diploma in Management of Innovation (Feb. 2008) from the Alta Scuola Politecnica (www.asp-poli.it). Following a six-month internship at the French Atomic Energy Commission – CEA-Saclay (France) – for his M.Sc. thesis from March to September 2007, he started in January 2008 his Ph.D. in Physics in co-tutorship between the Politecnico di Milano and the École Polytechnique X (Paris, France) under the guidance of Prof. Alberto Tagliaferri, Dr. Nicholas Barrett, and Prof. Henri-Jean Drouhin (*Italian/French joint degree*). During his Ph.D., Dr. Vanacore worked on the investigation of electronic and structural properties of semiconductor nanostructures using spectro-microscopy techniques. In November 2011, he joined as Postdoctoral Scholar the group of Prof. Ahmed H. Zewail (1999 Nobel Laureate in Chemistry) at the California Institute of Technology (Caltech), where his research activity was focused on the investigation of ultrafast phenomena in nanomaterials by means of ultrafast electron diffraction and ultrafast electron microscopy. In February 2016, he moved to Switzerland at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) joining the group of Prof. Fabrizio Carbone as Scientist. During his stay at EPFL, he was awarded an International Fellowship co-founded by Marie Skłodowska-Curie (March 2016, H2020 – MSCA – COFUND 2016, GA n. 665667). Here, he explored new methods for the coherent longitudinal and transverse phase manipulation

of a free-electron wave function using light pulses with attosecond precision, and demonstrated for the first time the generation of ultrafast vortex electron pulses. In March 2018, Dr. Vanacore obtained the Italian national academic qualification as associate professor in experimental matter physics. Since December 2019, he is a Tenure Track Assistant Professor at the University of Milano-Bicocca and head of the Laboratory of Ultrafast Microscopy for Nanoscale Dynamics (LUMiNaD), where his activity is dedicated to the investigation of ultrafast phenomena in nanoscale low-dimensional materials using ultrafast electron microscopy. For his research activities, he gave more than 20 invited talks at international conferences. He is author and co-author of 31 peer-reviewed publications in high impact factor journals (such as Nature Materials, Nature Communications, Science Advances, Physical Review Letters, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA, Nano Letters). His current h-index is 14 (from Scopus). From November 2018, he is co-PI together with Prof. Fabrizio Carbone of the “Project Heidi: Stimulated Nuclear Excitation by Electron Capture” founded by Google Inc. Dr. Vanacore is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Vanacore will be the project coordinator and principal investigator for UNIMIB. He will be involved in the activities related to all work packages.

Prof. Piercarlo Mustarelli, Ph.D. (male, born 03-07-1959). Physicist, he has more than 30 years of experience in the research and development of advanced functional materials for electrochemical energy conversion and storage, including batteries and fuel cells. During '80, Mustarelli worked to the development of innovative NMR instrumentation (several papers and two patents). This large experience allowed him to obtain the Cariplo Prize for Frontier Research in Chemistry 2011, thanks to the project “Electrochemical NMR microscope: the ultimate challenge”. The Prize jury included, among the others, the Nobel medalists Aaron Ciechanover and Gerhard Ertl. Currently, his research activity is mainly focused on the study of the correlation between structural and transport properties in functional materials for electrochemical devices. Since 2018 he is Full Professor of Physical Chemistry and Electrochemistry at DMS-UNIMIB. He organized several top-level events in the field of electrochemistry, including the ISE Conference 1999 celebrating the 200 years of Volta's discovery of pile. He is in the Editorial Board of several high-impact “peer-reviewed” journals. He authored/co-authored 259 papers on international peer-reviewed journals (SCOPUS), and holds 6 international patents. Google Scholar h-index = 49, with about 8700 citations (May 2020). Scopus h-index = 42, with more than 7200 citations (May 2020).

Role in the project: Prof. Mustarelli will coordinate and supervise the fabrication of electrochemical samples for the activities related to WP4.

Prof. Riccardo Ruffo, Ph.D. (male, born 20-04-1972). Electrochemist and expert of materials structure, he has 20 years of experience in the study of functional materials for electrochemical devices including batteries, fuel cells and electrochromic systems. Since 2015, he is Associate Professor at DMS-UNIMIB. During his career, he has been Visiting Scholar at the Stanford University with Prof. Yi Cui and Prof. R. A. Huggins (2008 and 2013) where he investigated the reaction of silicon nanowires in battery electrodes. His research interests are currently: inorganic materials for energy production and storage (alkaline ion batteries, supercaps), semi-conducting polymers and molecular materials for electro-optical applications (photovoltaic and electrochromism). Recent collaborations include: Prof. Do Kyung Kim (Korean Advanced Institute for Technology), Prof. Yi Cui (Stanford University) on nanostructured electrodes for lithium and sodium ion batteries. He is also involved in applied research on organic based electro-chromic materials for ophthalmic and smart windows (with the Fraunhofer Institute, Wurzburg). He was involved (partner or PI) in national, regional, and EU funding projects. He has authored/co-authored about more than 120 peer-reviewed papers (117 ISI), his h-indexes are 38 (Scholar) and 36 (WoS), the total citations are 7050 (Scholar).

Role in the project: Prof. Ruffo will be in charge of the fabrication of electrochemical samples for the activities related to WP4.

Dr. Luisa Fiandra (female). Dr. Fiandra is Researcher and Aggregate Professor in Cytology and Comparative Anatomy at the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences (DISAT), University of

Milano Bicocca, and she is member of the Research Center POLARIS (Particular Matter and Health Risk) and of the Nanotoxicology Laboratory of UNIMIB. From 2010 to 2017, Dr. Fiandra coordinated pre-clinical studies mainly devoted to the use of nanotechnology for cancer therapy and diagnosis, and for biological barriers overcoming. In this sense, Dr. Fiandra designed and supervised in vitro and in vivo experiments aimed to assess nanoparticles 1) interaction, internalization and trafficking in cells and animal tissues, 2) biological activity on target and non-target cells, 3) ability in crossing biological barriers (i.e., BBB) in vitro and in vivo, biodistribution, pharmacokinetic properties, therapeutic effect, and acute and sub-acute toxicity in murine models. From 2018, Dr. Fiandra is involved in the safety evaluation of different types of nanoproducts by in vitro assays and on alternative vertebrate models (Zebrafish). Dr. Fiandra is author of 34 publications in peer-reviewed journals. Total citations (22/05/2020): 639; H-index: 15 (Scopus). Dr. Fiandra is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Fiandra will be in charge of the nanoparticle synthesis and biological sample preparation for the activities related to WP5.

Prof. Davide Prosperi (male). Full Professor in Biochemistry at the University of Milano Bicocca, Department of Biotechnology and Bioscience. Principal investigator of the NanoBioLab of Unimib, he is devoted to biomedical and biophysical applications of nanotechnology. In particular, his research activity involves the design, synthesis, functionalization and characterization of colloidal, polymeric and biomimetic nanoparticles, and the study of their interaction with biological targets. He is an author of 121 scientific publications, including 106 research articles in peer-reviewed international scientific journals with impact factor and 5 book chapters. Total citations (22/05/2020): 3000; H-index: 28 (Scopus). Prof. Prosperi is one of the author of the patent "Nanoconstructs with pharmacological activity" (n° WO2014013473-A1), and he is co-founder of the spin-off company inTHEna srl, aiming to design and development of molecules, nanostructures and technologies for biomedical studies and diagnosis, prevention and therapy of human and animal diseases. Prof. Prosperi is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Prof. Prosperi will coordinate and supervise the nanoparticle synthesis and biological sample preparation for the activities related to WP5.

Prof. Fabrizio Carbone (male, born 20-04-1976). Prof. Fabrizio Carbone graduated in quantum electronics from the University of Pavia, Italy in 2001. He worked as an industrial researcher at Pirelli Labs, Milan, until 2002 when he started his PhD at the University of Groningen, The Netherlands. He obtained his PhD in condensed matter physics from the University of Geneva, Switzerland, and moved to Caltech for a Postdoc in 2007 in group of prof. Zewail (Nobel laureate for chemistry in 1999). In 2009 he moved back to Switzerland, at the EPFL, where he became assistant professor in 2010 and started the Laboratory for Ultrafast Microscopy and Electron Scattering (LUMES). During his stay at Caltech, he demonstrated the first femtosecond electron energy loss spectroscopy experiments in a transmission electron microscope, opening the field of ultrafast electron spectroscopic imaging which he developed in the following years in his own EPFL laboratory. He has been and currently is involved (as partner or PI) in many national, regional, and EU funding projects. He has authored/co-authored more than 100 peer-reviewed papers with a h-index of 25 (Scopus). Prof. Carbone is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Prof. Carbone will be principal investigator for EPFL. He will coordinate and supervise the experimental characterization of PELMs (WP1), their practical realization (WP2), and the implementation of Ramsey-type holography (WP3).

Dr. Ivan Madan (male, born 24-08-1988). Ivan Madan has graduated from Taras Shevchenko National University of Kiev, with a master degree in physics and specialization in photonics. He did his PhD in the group of prof. Mihailovic in Jozef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia, working on ultrafast studies of various superconductors, mastering various ultrafast techniques in particular broadband spectroscopy, high-pressure and high-magnetic ultrafast spectroscopies and ultrafast control of superconducting nano-circuits. In 2016 dr. Madan joins the group of Fabrizio Carbone at EPFL as a postdoc, where he implements first ultrafast Lorentz-TEM measurements, develops non-local holographic technique and shows how ultrafast TEM can increase energy resolution by two orders of magnitude. He is among the key

researchers of the group working electron-light interaction and electron-wavefunction engineering. Overall he is an author of 14 publication with 270 citations and h-index 9, has been granted synchrotron and high-field proposals, and has co-authored the 0.4 MUSD project on electron-nuclear interactions funded by Google Inc.

Role in the project: Dr. Madan will conduct the experimental characterization of PELMs (WP1), their practical realization (WP2) and the implementation of Ramsey-type holography (WP3).

Dr. Siham Benabib (female, born 31-08-1988). Dr. Benhabib graduated in condensed matter and nanotechnology from Pierre et Marie Curie - Sorbonne University - Paris, France, in 2012. She joined the group of Prof. Alain Sacuto in Paris Diderot-Sorbonne university-Paris to start her PhD. During her PhD, she investigated the electronic states of high T_c superconductors cuprates extensively using electronic Raman scattering. In 2016, she moved to Toulouse-France to join the group of Cyril Proust at the national laboratory of High magnetic fields (LNCMI-T) as a postdoctoral researcher. During the three years of her postdoc, she has been involved in various projects of strongly correlated systems such as high T_c superconductors and unconventional superconductors, which she used a high pulsed magnetic field up to 90 T combined to multiple techniques like electrical transport, ultrasounds, and contactless transport measurements. In 2019, she joined the group of Prof. Fabrizio Carbone as a postdoctoral researcher. Currently, her center of interest is the investigation of quantum critical phenomena in 2D material through ultrafast electron diffraction. In parallel, she is deeply involved in the study of high T_c superconductors by time-resolved and angle-resolved photo-emission (tr-ARPES). She has authored/co-authored 11 peer-reviewed papers with an h-index of 6 (Scopus). Dr. Benhabib is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Benabib will work on the application of the Ramsey-type holography method on strongly-correlated materials (WP3).

Ms. Veronica Leccese (female, born 08-06-1992). Mrs. Leccese graduated in Physics from the University of Pisa in 2018. In her master thesis, she worked on the simulations and the microfabrication of Terahertz Quantum Cascade Lasers (QCLs) with graphene waveguides. In 2019 she joined the group of Prof. Fabrizio Carbone at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), where she started her PhD. She is currently working on the generation, characterization, and detection of twisted matter waves ('vortex beams'). In particular, her work is focused on the nanofabrication of phase plates, which allow generating twisted matter waves, their characterization with an Ultrafast Transmission Electron Microscope, and the fabrication of microfluidic detectors aimed to detect vortex beams. She is a cleanroom user and she has experience in nano-microfabrication technology. Mrs. Leccese is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Ms. Leccese will conduct the experimental characterization of PELMs (WP1) and work on their practical realization (WP2).

Prof. F. Javier García de Abajo (male, born 6-12-1964). Javier García de Abajo received his PhD from the University of the Basque Country in 1993 and then visited Lawrence Berkeley National Lab for three years. He was a Research Professor at the Spanish CSIC and in 2013 moved to ICFO-Institut de Ciències Fotoniques (Barcelona) as an ICREA Research Professor, where he leads the Nanophotonics Theory Group. His research agenda includes the theoretical study of electron microscope spectroscopies, graphene and two-dimensional plasmonics, atomic collisions, quantum phenomena at the nanoscale, and various aspects of nanophotonics ranging from optical sensing to quantum friction. García de Abajo has co-authored 400+ articles (~20 papers per year over the last decade), cited 30,000+ times with a h-index of 83 (June 2020 Web of Science data, see ResearcherID A-6095-2009). He is co-inventor in 7 patents and his papers have been selected for 26 journal covers. He has delivered 223 invited talks, including 30 keynotes and 12 plenaries. He is a Fellow of both the American Physical Society and the Optical Society of America, and he has been awarded the 2019 Science of Light Prize by the European Physical Society. He has supervised 10 PhD students and 20 postdocs and is currently embarked in the development of

improved spatially-resolved electron spectroscopies funded by an Advanced ERC grant and aiming at the achievement of sub-fs, sub-nm, sub-meV combined resolutions.

Role in the project: Prof. García de Abajo will be principal investigator for ICFO. He will coordinate and supervise the theoretical activities across all the work packages in the SMART-electron project.

Dr. Andrea Konečná (female, born 21-3-1991). Graduated cum laude in the PhD program "Physics of Nanostructures and Advanced Materials" at the University of the Basque Country. She developed her PhD thesis in the Theory of Nanophotonics Group led by Javier Aizpurua and in her thesis, she theoretically studied optical and vibrational response of nanostructures as probed by fast electrons. Andrea has developed skills in analytical and numerical modeling of electron energy spectroscopy and successfully collaborated on several projects with experimental groups in the field of electron microscopy. Since June 2020, she is a postdoctoral researcher at ICFO in the Nanophotonics Theory Group of Javier García de Abajo and continues working on projects related to fast electron spectroscopy and relevant for the proposed project. She has participated, e.g., in a theoretical proposal of optical phase plate for correction of beam aberrations, or has studied the possibility of detecting nonlinear optical response in electron spectra.

Role in the project: Dr. Andrea Konečná will contribute to the simulation of electron-beam/sample interactions.

Dr. Vahagn Mkhitarian (male, born 11-01-1989). Earned his PhD (summa cum laude) in Nanophotonics from Universidad Politécnic de Cataluña (UPC) at ICFO. During his PhD, Vahagn combined theoretical and experimental methods to study photonic properties of thin films and periodic arrays of scatterers. This allowed him to master various computational skills including simulations and analytical modelling of photonic systems as well as cutting-edge fabrication and optical characterization methods. Since 2017, Vahagn is a Postdoctoral researcher in the Nanophotonics Theory group at ICFO. In the group, he conducts experimental and theoretical studies on the plasmonic properties of atomically thin, crystalline silver films. He also theoretically studies the interaction of electron beams with optical modes. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Vahagn Mkhitarian will use extensive numerical calculations for sample and phase mask designs.

Dr. Shahaf Asban (male, born 27-01-1981). PhD from the Faculty of Physics at Technion (Israel), former postdoc at the University of California at Irvine (USA). In his PhD Shahaf became an expert in the theory of fluctuating thermodynamics of systems far from equilibrium, and mathematical modeling of strongly driven system in a noisy environment. In late 2017, Shahaf joined UCI as a postdoctoral fellow, focusing on spectroscopy with quantum states of light and its quantum information aspects. Especially relevant to this proposal, Shahaf is an expert in designing quantum-enhanced measurement protocols aimed to extract information exclusive to quantum probes.

Role in the project: Dr. Shahaf Asban will analyse quantum aspects of electron-beam/sample interactions.

Dr. Fadil Iyikanat (male, born 11-8-1987). Fadil Iyikanat is a postdoctoral researcher in the Nanophotonics Theory Group at ICFO. He completed his Ph.D. in theoretical condensed matter physics at İzmir Institute of Technology, Turkey, in 2019. During his Ph.D. he gained deep experience on theoretical concepts of solid state physics, numerical methods and computer simulations, performing density functional theory simulations to calculate electronic and optical properties of nanostructured materials. The numerical and advanced computational methods will definitely improve the quality of research in the proposed project by helping to predict and understand ultrafast material's response and experimental data. He has published more than 20 articles in international peer-reviewed journals. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Fadil Iyikanat will perform ab initio calculations of electron-beam/sample interactions.

Mr. Álvaro Rodríguez Echarri (male, born 22-08-1993). BSc Physics from the Autonomous University of Barcelona, he obtained the MSc Photonics diploma at the Abbe School of Photonic in the Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, and he is currently a PhD candidate at ICFO under the supervision of Prof. Javier García de Abajo. During his degree and graduate studies, he acquired experience in high harmonic generation in gases, self-compression on gas filled hollow fibers, light with orbital angular momentum, and modulation instability and nonlinear dynamics in planar microcavities. Nowadays, his research expertise developed in his PhD pertains to the theoretical modelling of linear and nonlinear optical phenomena in few-atom thick crystalline metal films; bridging the realms of 2D atomically-thin materials such as graphene with 3D bulk crystals. In his third year of PhD, he has published 4 peer-review papers, and participated in international conferences with more than 15 contributions, counting posters, contributed and invited talks. Since May 2020, he is the representative of the Nanophotonic Youth Committee in the Spanish Optical Society, as well as OSA and SPIE member. In the MSc, he graduated as the best student of the year 2017 and is the second best out of 97 graduates in the last 6 semesters. Recently, he has been awarded with the 2020 - SPIE Optics and Photonics Education Scholarship for his potential contributions to the field of optics, photonics or related field.

Role in the project: Mr. Álvaro Rodríguez Echarri will contribute to ab initio calculations of electron-beam/sample interactions.

Mr. Eduardo Dias (male, born 21-01-1994). Obtained his MSc in Fundamental Physics at the University of Minho, Portugal. During his MSc, Eduardo focused on the study of the plasmonic properties of graphene-based heterostructures, with special focus on periodic systems. During this time, Eduardo developed both analytical and semi-analytical codes to describe the optical properties of such structures. Since 2017, Eduardo is pursuing a PhD in Photonics at ICFO, Spain, where he works on the theory of polaritonics in thin materials, focusing on their effective excitation and manipulation, including interactions with electron beams. For this purpose, he uses self-developed codes, as well as COMSOL simulations and other codes developed by the hosting group. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Mr. Eduardo Dias will use extensive numerical calculations for sample and phase mask designs.

Mr. Valerio Di Giulio (male, born 10-9-1993). Summa cum laude in his BSc and MSc in Theoretical Physics at “Università, La Sapienza”, Rome. During his BSc’s thesis, he focused on Monte Carlo and molecular dynamics simulations to study the role played by electromagnetic forces into the formation of cholesteric phases of DNAs in solution. In his MSc, Valerio kept focusing mostly on the study of statistical mechanics and critical phenomena then turning his attention to quantum information. In particular, he developed his MSc’s thesis in Prof. Fabio Sciarrino’s laboratory to demonstrate both theoretically and experimentally a new Bell-like inequality. After his master, he started his on-going PhD under the supervision of Prof. Javier García de Abajo in order to theoretically study new phenomena in electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) and photon- induced near-field electron microscopy (PINEM) performed in transition electron microscopes. Of primal importance for the proposed project, Valerio has extensively worked with both theoretical and numerical tools to study quantum effects in the interaction between fast electrons and light, especially in the calculation of electron spectra and cathodoluminescence intensities. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Mr. Valerio Di Giulio will contribute to the simulation of electron-beam/sample interactions and will contribute to the analysis of quantum aspects of electron-beam/sample interactions.

Dr. Ido Kaminer (male, born 29-12-1985). Dr. Kaminer is assistant professor at the Department of Electrical Engineering, joined the Technion as an Azrieli Faculty Fellow in March 2018, after a postdoc at MIT as a Rothschild Fellow, MIT-Technion Fellow, and a Marie Curie Fellow. In his PhD, Prof. Kaminer

discovered new classes of accelerating beams in nonlinear optics and electromagnetism, for which he received the 2012 Israel Physical Society Prize, and the 2014 APS (American Physical Society) Award for Outstanding Doctoral Dissertation in Laser Science. Prof. Kaminer was the first Israeli to ever win an APS award for his PhD thesis. He currently holds the Technion's Jacques Lewiner Career Advancement Chair – Leaders in Science and Technology. Prof. Kaminer won multiple awards and grants recently, including the GIF Young Scientists Grant and the ERC Starting Grant. Prof. Kaminer research is focused on applications of quantum electrodynamics to address fundamental and applied problems in Optics, Photonics, Plasmonics and Electron Microscopy. His group develops experiments that combine femtosecond lasers and electron microscopes. They study light-matter interactions in nanophotonics and in 2D material platforms, with applications for novel light sources and ultrafast detectors. He is author and co-author of 79 journal publications; total citations >2900; h-index 28. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Kaminer will be principal investigator for TECHNION. He will coordinate and supervise the experimental implementation of the Quantum-CL method (WP5), and support the characterization and realization of PELMs as detailed in WP1 and WP2.

Dr. Kangpeng Wang (male, born in March 1988). Dr. Wang is a postdoctoral researcher at the Department of Electrical Engineering in Technion as a Lady Davis Fellow from June 2017. He obtained his PhD in optical materials from Shanghai Institute of Optics and Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, in 2013. During his PhD, he received the President Award of the Chinese Academy of Sciences and National PhD Scholarship of Chinese Education Ministry. After that, he moved to Trinity College Dublin for a postdoc in the group of Prof. Werner Blau in ultrafast spectroscopy and was involved in the ISLA project under EU FP7. He received the Irish 66th Lindau Nobel Laureate Meeting Fellowship. In 2017, he joined the Technion as the first postdoc in the group of Prof. Ido Kaminer. During his work at the Technion, he was involved in building of a new ultrafast transmission electron microscope. He has authored/co-authored 24 peer-reviewed papers with total citations >2100 and an h-index of 16 (Google Scholar). Dr. Kangpeng Wang is a first-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Dr. Wang will be in charge of the experimental implementation of the Quantum-CL method (WP5), and participate in the characterization and realization of PELMs as detailed in WP1 and WP2.

Mr. Raphael Dahan (male). Summa cum laude in his MSc in Mechanical Engineering at the Technion. In his MSc, Raphael became an expert in theory and experiments on micro resonator optics for different applications. During that time, he did electro-magnetic simulations in Comsol, advanced mechanical designs, and work with fiber optics. Since early 2018, Raphael is the lab engineer of the Technion UTEM Lab. He was involved in establishing the UTEM Lab and in all the UTEM projects since it began. Especially important for the proposed project, Raphael is an expert in the optical design of the UTEM and will lead the modifications needed to allow efficient light collection for cathodoluminescence and SLM integration in the existing UTEM at the Technion. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Mr. Dahan will be in charge of the experimental implementation of the Quantum-CL method (WP5).

Mr. Michael Yannai (male, born in March 1989). Michael is a PhD student at the Department of Electrical Engineering at Technion from November 2019. He obtained his MSc (Cum Laude) in optics and BSc (Cum Laude) in optical engineering from the Department of Mechanical Engineering at Technion. During his MSc, Michael studied light-matter interactions in nano-photonic devices, focusing on multispectral and random metasurfaces. His research included both theoretical aspects and experimental work, combining fundamental studies in physics and optics and the development of application-oriented technology. He received the Russell Berrie Nanotechnology Institute (RBNI) scholarship during his MSc and the KLA-Tencor scholarship during his BSc. In the past year, Michael has developed a theoretical model encompassing a broad class of interactions between free-electrons and electronic potentials. He aims to utilize this theory to study various phenomena, such as plasma dynamics, terahertz radiation

generation and control, charge transport in semi-conductors and more. 7 journal publications; total citations >150; h-index 4. First-time participant to FET under Horizon 2020.

Role in the project: Mr. Yannai will conduct the experimental implementation of the Quantum-CL method (WP5) and participate in the theoretical characterization of PELMs as detailed in WP1.

Dr. V. Grillo (male, born 20-10-1973). Vincenzo Grillo is the Scientific Coordinator and Principal Investigator of Q-SORT. He graduated in physics from the University of Genova (110/110 cum laude). He received his PhD in electron microscopy at the University of Parma, while performing collaborative work with Erlangen University (Germany). In 2001 he was a visiting scientist at the Tokyo Institute of Technology working on cathodoluminescence in TEM. Since 2003 he has been working at INFM (the Italian National Institute for the Physics of Matter - now part of CNR) as a Senior Fellow researcher in electron microscopy. He has developed innovative TEM-STEM methodology and published the first quantitative use of STEM with HAADF detector for chemical analysis. He is now working on vortex beams and holographic beam generation. He and his group are now among the world's leading groups in this sector for their work on phase holograms, large vortex beams, and the theory of spin-orbit coupling with vortex. In 2015 he was a visiting researcher at the University of Oregon. In 2016 he received the Humboldt Foundation's Bessel research award for his work on beam shaping. Dr. Grillo is co-author of more than 100 articles and 5 book chapters. The H-index of his publications is 34.

Role in the project: Dr. Grillo will be principal investigator for CNR. He will coordinate and supervise the activities of CNR within WP1, WP2 and WP4. He will also support UNIMIB in the coordination of the project (WP6) thanks to his experience as coordinator of the Q-SORT FET-Open project.

Dr Enzo Rotunno (male, 29-4-1986). Enzo Rotunno (graduated magna cum laude in Material Science at the University of Parma in 2010 and obtained his PhD degree in material science from the same institution in 2014. Since 2014 he has a research fellow position at the Italian National Research Council. During his career he achieved high competence in the field of Transmission Electron Microscopy mastering the main electron imaging, diffraction and spectroscopic techniques, with his main research interest being the study of materials through STEM with HAADF detector and the developed of numerical algorithms for the simulation of the electron-matter interaction. He currently works in CNR-NANO Quantum e-optics group among the world's leading groups in the field of electron vortex beams, and the theory of spin-orbit coupling with vortex. Recently he has started a theoretical activity related to the development of deep learning techniques for microscopy. Dr. Rotunno is co-author of more than 40 research paper. The H-index of his publications is 13.

Role in the project: Dr. Rotunno will be in charge of developing the deep-learning algorithm (WP2) and will support the implementation of a compressive-sensing algorithm (WP4).

Dr. Gian Carlo Gazzadi (male). Dr. Gazzadi received his PhD in Physics from the University of Modena in 1997. He is a Senior Technologist at the CNR-NANO-S3 center in Modena where he is the coordinator of the nanofabrication facility. His primary research interest are the nanofabrication with Dual Beam focused ion beam (FIB) – scanning electron microscope (SEM) systems. FIB activity includes: nanofabrication of holographic plates and samples for electron interference experiments, nanopatterning of surfaces for nanomagnetism and nanotribology studies, fabrication of nanogap electrodes, nanomachining of scanning probe tips. Regarding electron-beam nanofabrication, the main interest is about focused electron beam-induced deposition (FEBID) of nanostructures from gas precursors, and their characterization from a structural and electrical viewpoint. He has 99 publications on international journals (ISI h-index 21), 3 book chapters, 1 national patent. He is member of the scientific committee of focused electron beam-induced processing (FEBIP) international workshop.

Role in the project: Dr. Gazzadi will conduct the micro-fabrication activities as described in WP1.

Dr. Giovanni Bertoni (male). Giovanni Bertoni obtained his PhD in Physics at the University of Milan in 2003 with a thesis on carbon nanostructured films, studied with microscopy and spectroscopy techniques.

From 2003 to 2008 he was a Post-Doc researcher in renowned European centers in the field of transmission electron microscopy and spectroscopy, such as the CEMES-CNRS of Toulouse (France) and EMAT of the University of Antwerp (Belgium). From 2008-2011 he was a scientist at the Italian Institute of Technology in Genova, establishing an advanced laboratory of electron microscopy, including the first image corrected transmission microscope in Italy. From 2011 he is a staff researcher at the CNR. He participated in the national (PRIN) project 'Hierarchical photosynthetic nanostructures for energy production' from 2013 to 2016. In 2020 he has received the Canada-Italy innovation award for the study of ion batteries in the TEM/STEM. G. Bertoni has consolidated experience in high resolution transmission microscopy (HRTEM) and scanning transmission microscopy (STEM), combined with electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS), both theoretically and experimentally and applied in particular to the study of nanostructured materials. He has published more than 100 scientific papers and 2 patents. The H-index of his publications is 39 (scholar).

Role in the project: Dr. Bertoni will participate in the characterization and realization of PELMs as detailed in WP1 and WP2, and will participate in the electrochemical experiments detailed in WP4.

Jean-Christophe Olaya (male) - Jean-Christophe Olaya is an optics engineer and holds a Master's Degree in Optics in Photonics from the Institut d'Optique Graduate School (Palaiseau, France) and a University Degree in Biomedical Specialisation. He worked as a developer for holographic displays at SeeReal Technologies (Dresden, Germany), Light Microscopy Facility Manager at the Biotechnologisches Zentrum der TU Dresden (Dresden, Germany), as Instrument Scientist and Fibre-lab Manager for the Leibniz-Institut für Astrophysics Potsdam (Potsdam, Germany), Project Manager for the Business Unit Metrology for SwissOptic (Heerbrugg, Switzerland), and as Development engineer for hyperspectral cameras at LLA Instruments (Berlin, Germany). He is currently Coordinator for Development projects for the Business Unit Microdisplay Technologies at HOLOEYE. His fields of expertise cover the topics of the image chain, from light source to sensor and data processing. He also has an extensive experience in Project Management in industrial and public research environment.

Role in the project: Dr. Olaya will be principal investigator for HOLOEYE. He will coordinate and supervise the hardware and software integration of SLM within the UTEM setups.

Friedemann Gädeke (male) - Friedemann Gädeke studied physics specialized to nano optics at Institut für Physik, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin (Berlin, Germany), in the workgroup Nano Optics. He was working with single photon sources and plasmonic structures (SPASER). In parallel, he worked as a research student at HOLOEYE Photonics mainly doing software development for the optical laboratory. Since 2016 he is employed full time by HOLOEYE Photonics and develops various kinds of software, including the customer software HOLOEYE SLM Configuration Manager and the HOLOEYE SLM Display SDK, which has bindings and examples for Python, LabVIEW, Matlab, Octave, and C/C++. He is also involved in optical characterization of the SLM devices under development. His fields of expertise cover optical engineering, software development, and software - hardware communication.

Role in the project: Dr. Gädeke will conduct the hardware and software integration of SLM within the UTEM setups.

Maytal Dvash (female) serves as a research supporter for Prof. Ido Kaminer. Prior, she managed Haifa's municipality tech hub, led and managed SigmaLab North- a tech accelerator powered by Sarona Venture Capital, and still mentors and supports entrepreneurship programs, including Sapir College Center for innovation and entrepreneurship, Road2Impact entrepreneurship program, and others.

Maytal holds a BA and MA in business management both from Haifa University. She specializes in entrepreneurship & innovation, business development, project management, team leading, industrial and collaboration relations.

Role in the project: Maytal will coordinate and supervise the Technion's administrative aspect of the project.

Raffaella Santucci (Female) specializes in project management, team building, institutional relations, knowledge transfer, outreach, and event planning. She has served as a consultant for several institutions, including Sapienza – University of Rome, Coventry University, the Auditorium in Rome (Musica per Roma), Sapienza Innovazione, Promoter SrL, Codice Idee per la Cultura, Wikimedia Italia and AEDEKA. On behalf of DISIT, University of Florence, she managed the networking and communication activities of the EC-funded project ECLAP (an E-Library for the Performing Arts). On behalf of Digilab, Sapienza, University of Rome, she worked as Project and Innovation Manager and Director of Communications for multiple EC-funded projects, including Linked Heritage, DiXiT: Digital Scholarly Editions Initial Training Network, and EAGLE: the Europeana network of Ancient Greek and Latin Epigraphy. On behalf of QED she acted as Executive Manager of the EC-funded project Q-SORT and MINEON.

Role in the project: Dr. Santucci will coordinate and supervise the dissemination and science communication activities as detailed in WP6.

Meet your scientist

Shai Tsesses

What is your specific area of research? How would you explain it to young children?

I am exploring many aspects of how light affects matter at the nano-scale, mostly through controlling plasmonic fields – surface waves of light. One of these aspects is how we can use plasmonic fields to shape free electrons, which is my part in this project. To put things in a more simplified perspective, I'm like a kid trying to put his hand in water, and wiggle it hard and fast enough so that the water would make an interesting shape, except instead of using my hand, I'm using light; and instead of shaping water, I'm shaping electrons (which are kind of like water).

Why did you choose your research field? Were you inspired by someone?

I wasn't really inspired by a person, but I just found that I really (really) like wave phenomena. I found that I understand every physical process through wave phenomena much better than I did through the regular way of explaining them. As an undergraduate student I tried looking for a job as research assistant in a lab that dealt with any kind of wave phenomenon in my department, and my current advisor is actually the only one that answered my email! The rest is history.

How does your life as a top scientist compare with your expectations of it when you enrolled in Physics?

I don't really think of myself as a "top" scientist. I'm just me, trying to lead my own life. Being a scientist is my job, but what's fun about it is that I can ask myself whatever questions I want and try to find answers. I think I'd be the same no matter what profession I'd take up, but being a scientist sure gives you much more freedom to explore!

What traits might a child possess that may indicate an interest or aptitude for your research field?

Curiosity and imagination. I wasn't born a physicist, but I always liked inventing stories, exploring histories and myths or trying to answer interesting puzzles. I think that anyone with the will to explore and imagine new things can be successful in our research field, they just have to agree to learn math as well!

What are you currently working on and what is your long-term research goal?

I'm currently trying to develop the technology to shape electron beams using surface waves of light, such that by controlling the shape or amplitude of the surface wave, I'd be able to control the shape of the electron beam. This mechanism is actually very similar to the Acousto-Optical Modulator in optics, but here the light plays the part of the acoustic waves. My long-term goal is for this technology to mature into an actual device, allowing us arbitrary control over electron beam shapes.

Do you have an analogy to help our readers to understand your work?

Sure. Think about the laser show in the last music festival you went to (I'm assuming it had a laser show), or the advanced surround-sound system that was used in the last movie you went to (do they still have those?). The laser show was able to produce various shapes in the sky by controlling the illumination

pattern, and the surround-sound system changed its sound projection according to the position of a car moving on the screen. Oddly as it may sound, we are now trying to do the same thing, but for streams of charged particles – electrons.

What is it that excites you about your work?

I like that it's at the interface between fundamental and applied physics. Obviously we're trying to create a technology that will be used for many different and important things, but at the same time – not all the questions are answered. We don't know what are the limits or how far we can push it yet, so it's always exciting to try and explore new frontiers.

Why is your research important?

It could solve a whole bunch of problems and open an unforeseeable amount of new applications, but I'm most excited about trying to use it to solve the global chip shortage. The main bottleneck in chip production is the need to replace lithography masks and realign the manufacturing systems every time you wish to produce a different chip. What if you didn't have to do that? What if you could just use electrons – without the need for scanning, mind you – to produce chips and never replace the mask, since it'll be programmable? I'm very much looking forward to seeing if we can help solve this very important problem.

Is there a story/anecdote about your work that you would like to share with us?

I think the way I found myself in my current project is pretty random. I was invited to a conference about controlling electron beams (presenting something completely unrelated), and I was exposed to this huge problem of trying to actively control electron beams. It's not so much that it was highlighted, but the state-of-the-art at the time left such a bad impression on me, that I thought "there has to be a better way to do it! This is a really important problem!". So I dedicated a lot of time and effort in order to try and realize it with the tools at my disposal.

Would you like to mention one or more of your most important scientific findings?

After several years of research, I am happy to say that we now have the capability to actively control electron beams using surface waves of light. We have more than one control knob, and we can produce electron shapes that are currently impossible in any other active device. I hope this will usher in a new era for electron microscopy, with a far better active control over electron beams.

What is it that you like to do when you aren't working on research?

I love writing sports articles for sports blogs! Especially about basketball and the NBA. I also enjoy singing and playing role-playing games with friends, but lately I just focus on spending time with my spouse and child whenever I get the chance.

Is there enough support/funding for science in Europe today? What could be improved in this respect, at a national level? And at European level?

I do not feel I have the tools to answer this question.

Now for the big picture: what is your assessment of the current state of your area of research? (i.e. where do you see it going, what expectations for the future, etc.)

There truly is a massive effort (2 European consortia, in addition to other groups in Europe as well as the US) who are currently pursuing the goal of a spatial electron modulator using light – a device that can produce arbitrary free-electron shapes through the interaction of light and free electrons. Much as in our own consortium of SMARTelectron, there are many approaches to this challenge. Our efforts for shaping using structured near-fields appear to currently be at the forefront, but other near-field related approaches and even approaches utilizing the ponderomotive force are progressing very fast. It is too soon to determine which approach will be optimal, but this is a very exciting time in the life of a field: where visions are rigorously pursued, to become realities. I expect that the next 5 years will see a vast improvement in capabilities, and by then we will know much better how close we can potentially get to our final goal.

Shai graduated from the Technion – Israel Institute of Technology in 2016, with a double B.Sc in Electrical Engineering and Physics, and is currently finishing his Ph.D Thesis on controlling the topology of light at the nanoscale and transferring it to matter. He is the recipient of the Jacobs Foundation fellowship, the

Adams fellowship of the Israel Academy of Sciences and Humanities and the OSA's Tingye Li innovation award.

Women in science

Luisa Fiandra, Milano Bicocca University

What is your specific area of research?

My specific research area is now the development of advanced 3D cells models of tumors to study their biological complexity and exploit this complexity to validate innovative nanoformulated therapies

How would you explain your research field to young children?

Like the worst of enemies, tumors protect themselves with physical barriers and developing defense strategies to survive. My research activity is aimed to study these defense systems, in order to find the way to overcome them. In particular, I will test the efficacy of new discovered drugs combined with nano-objects, to fight tumors more efficiently.

What traits might a child possess that may indicate an interest or aptitude for your research field?

Curiosity about the things of nature, wondering what everything they see is made of and how they work, and a great passion for discovery

What did you know about your field when you were a child?

Actually, I did not know so much about biomedical research, but I was very curious about everything living in nature, of all sizes and complexities.

Why did you choose your research field? Were you inspired by someone?

I initially chose to study life sciences for a real passion for animal biology with a focus on insect physiology. Then, after the PhD, almost 12 years ago, I got a great offer from two great scientists and men: the first is an expert of nanobiotechnology, the other an important breast cancer surgeon. They decided to face a big challenge together: to prevent and fight cancer using nanoparticles. This project was the beginning of a long and charming story in the field of nano-oncology.

What are some really cool things that people in your profession work on?

In my opinion, a really cool thing in my area of expertise is now represented by the use of nanoparticle-based vaccines for the modulation of pathways involved in pathologies, including cancer. Different nanoformulations have been recently developed for the delivery of mRNA for cancer immunotherapy.

Do you have an analogy to help our readers to understand your work?

As I told before, the best analogy of my work is a fight against the great enemy, cancer, able to develop strategies to be more aggressive and defend itself from the attack of anti-tumor drugs, the weapons used to defeat him.

Is there a story/anecdote about your work that you would like to share with us?

How does your life as a top scientist compare with your expectations when you entered college?

When I started studying Life Sciences, I had no idea of what could be the life of a scientist and the impact that this work could have on issues related to human health. If, on the one hand, I found exciting the possibility of discovering new and more effective therapies, on the other hand, I was faced with the difficulty to translate these discoveries into clinically effective drugs. In this sense, I am now aware of the enormous power of cooperation between academia and biopharma companies.

What are you currently working on and what is your long-term research goal?

I am studying the complexity of interactions between tumor cells and the microenvironment, with a focus on the cross-talk between cancer cells and Cancer-Associated Fibroblasts (CAFs) in highly aggressive desmoplastic tumors (i.e. pancreatic adenocarcinoma, small cells lung tumors, some breast cancer types

etc.). The different pathways activated by the soluble factors released by tumor cells and CAFs, and responsible for the high aggressiveness, metastasizing power and drug resistance of these tumors, can be exploited as targets of new therapies, included nanoformulated vaccines.

Are there still gender differences in your research environment and what are current opportunities and challenges for women in science?

I no longer appreciate gender differences in my institution. In my department (dep. of Biotechnology and Biosciences of University of Milano Bicocca) there are many women, and many of them hold high-profile academic roles.

Why is your research important?

The importance of my research is related to the high difficulty that still today we have in defeating some tumors that have a disastrous prognosis, like the pancreatic adenocarcinoma or some aggressive breast cancer subtypes. These tumors, which are very aggressive and defend themselves from chemotherapy by accurate resistance strategies must be the object of innovative anti-tumor therapies aimed to target the complex biological interactions between the tumor cells and the microenvironment components.

Is there enough support/funding for science in Europe today? What could be improved in this respect, at a national and European level?

Today, the possibility of funding from Europe exists and concerns various scientific fields, including the biomedical one. Of course the European calls (H2020) are designed for very huge projects, often including the initiation of clinical trials, and therefore directed towards large networks. Beyond a few exceptions, such as for example SMART-electron project, where young brilliant scientists were able to implement innovative ideas thanks to the institution of large international groups, most of the projects funded by EU include big research groups headed by eminent full professors that already receive support at the national level. In my opinion, today more opportunities of funding for small research groups with innovative scientific ideas are possible in Italy, even if they could be further improved: more value should be attributed to ideas, so that any scientist with sufficient expertise to carry out his/her idea, can have space and opportunities.

What inspirational message would you give young girls to inspire them to pursue a career in science?

I can say to all young girls to pursue this goal with commitment and passion. The women of science have characteristics that are real strengths. We never should doubt this high potentiality, in particular in a male working context. The integration of male and female approaches to scientific problems are certainly a wealth, such as those given by each unique and personal characteristic.

Luisa Fiandra is Researcher and Assistant Professor in Clinical Biochemistry at the Department of Biotechnology and Biosciences of University of Milano Bicocca (Unimib). Since 2010, LF has coordinated pre-clinical studies mainly devoted to the use of nanotechnology for cancer therapy and diagnosis, and for biological barriers overcoming. These in vitro and in vivo studies were aimed to assess nanoparticles interaction, internalization and trafficking in cells and animal tissues, the biological activity on target and non-target cells, and the ability in crossing biological barriers, such as the biodistribution, pharmacokinetic properties, therapeutic effect, and acute and sub-acute toxicity of nanoformulations in murine models. From 2018, LF has participated to EU projects aimed to determine the toxicity of different types of nanoproducts by in vitro assays and on alternative vertebrate models (Zebrafish), in line with the Safe-by-Design concept for the development of new nanoformulated nanotools. Currently, LF is mainly devoted to the use of advanced cellular models for the validation of conventional or latest generation therapies directed towards tumor pathologies. In particular, the research activity is now mainly focused on the study of innovative strategies involving tumor microenvironment cells to eradicate desmoplastic tumors. LF is also member of Centro 3R (Inter-University Center for the Promotion of the 3Rs Principles in Teaching & Research), and of the BioNanoMedicine Center "NANOMIB" and POLARIS research Centre (study of the impact of nanomaterials and pollution on environment and health) of Unimib.

Veronica Leccese

What is your specific area of research?

I'm working in two different areas: the first one is condensed matter physics, the second one is nano/microtechnology.

How would you explain your research field to young children?

I'm studying the magnetic properties of some materials which in the future could be useful for storing enormous quantities of data in very small dimensions. In addition to that, I'm developing a beam profiler to characterize proton beams, for experiments of fundamental physics but also for medical purposes since protons are used in proton therapy to treat some kinds of tumors.

What traits might a child possess that may indicate an interest or aptitude for your research field?

In my opinion the traits that a researcher should have are curiosity, the desire to always learn something new, perseverance and stubbornness. Everyday in our job, we need to face and solve problems, so if you're not persistent and headstrong enough.

What did you know about your field when you were a child?

Almost nothing. I was attracted to scientific subjects, I loved math, but I've never considered becoming a physicist before I was 19. When I was in middle school, one of my teachers started to express her admiration towards mathematicians, at that moment I decided to become a mathematician. However, when I started university, I realized that I was much more attracted by the experimental work, so after a few weeks, I decided to enroll in physics. I have to say that it was a good choice!

Why did you choose your research field? Were you inspired by someone?

I was challenged. Everybody around me kept saying that physics was one of the most difficult subjects, so I decided to try and accept the challenge. Why condensed matter/microtechnology? Condensed Matter is a fascinating world for me. I love discovering new things that can be used in the future to improve the quality of life of people. As a physicist, this field keeps my curiosity alive. Microtechnology for my engineering side (yes, I have one!). I love fabricating stuff by myself and use them afterwards.

What are some really cool things that people in your profession work on?

I'm surrounded by people who are working on amazing things such as electron diffraction, spectrometry, optics, but also MEMs and devices with many purposes.

How does your life as a top scientist compare with your expectations of it when you enrolled in Physics?

When I enrolled in Physics I wasn't really aware of which could have been my path. I was looking at the researchers with a huge admiration. At that time I didn't know how much work and effort was hidden behind this job. When I started I realize that you have to be very motivated and willing to make a lot of sacrifices. So I have to say that from outside it seems a normal job, but it is not. If you're not passionate, you cannot do it.

What are you currently working on and what is your long-term research goal?

I'm working on the generation of vortex beams, mainly electrons for now, that can be used to study the magnetic properties of some materials. The other project I'm working on is the realization of a beam profiler for protons with the aim of controlling the proton beam during the proton therapy, which is used to treat some tumors.

Are there still gender differences in your research environment and what are current opportunities and challenges for women in science?

Unfortunately yes. More than one time it happened to me to not be considered by other scientists because I'm a woman. That's sad, but sometimes it still happens.

Why is your research important?

The project related to the vortex beams I think is important because they might allow us to discover new properties of materials that in future could be used for the storage of a huge amount of data. The project of the detector for protons is important because, as you can imagine, during the therapy with the protons, it is crucial to control the parameters of the beam, since a wrong parameter could kill the patients.

Is there enough support/funding for science in Europe today? What could be improved in this respect, at a national and European level?

In my opinion no, there isn't enough support. I think that the number of researchers has increased in the last years, but the funding/support has not. I have to say that at EPFL we have a lot of support, but it is not the case in Italy, where I studied. I would try to give the same opportunity to all the European countries.

What inspirational message would you give young girls to inspire them to pursue a career in science? If you're passionate and you'd like to work in the most stimulating environment, a career in science is your way!

Graduated in Physics at the University of Pisa in 2018. In 2019 I joined the group of Prof. Fabrizio Carbone at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), where I started my PhD.

SCIENCE

A layperson's introduction to SE

For a long time, progress in Electron Microscopy (EM) has been equated with the art of obtaining images of increasingly higher resolution: instrumental research was mainly aimed at obtaining a very small probe and aberration-free images. A swift change of paradigm has occurred during recent years, when the first ideas of electron-beam shaping were introduced. The main idea is to use properly designed holograms and electrostatic and magnetostatic phase elements to manipulate both phase and amplitude of the free-electron in a nearly arbitrary manner. A new way of conceiving EM is thus underway, with the potential to achieve enhanced performance and to measure new physical quantities.

The field of electron wavefunction engineering has mainly originated from light optics due to the strong analogy between electron and photon wave optics. For a variety of reasons, in this field experiments with photons are easier and cheaper to realise than the corresponding ones with electrons: it is therefore natural to wonder whether electron manipulation could benefit even further from such a precious connection with light. The first idea in this sense has been the development of photon-assisted electron emission in a transmission electron microscope (TEM). This has prompted the creation of Ultrafast Electron Microscopy (UEM), which allows dynamical investigation of materials on the femtosecond time scale, such as lattice vibrations, charge dynamics, and plasmonics. This technique is based on the so-called pump-and-probe scheme, whereby a laser excites the sample and a carefully-timed ultrashort electron pulse then probes its non-equilibrium status. One recent evolution of such an approach is the Photon-Induced Near-field Electron Microscopy (PINEM) method, which is able to transiently probe near-fields at the nanoscale, using an electron microscope. These experiments showed that nanometer-sized structures can be employed to produce uniquely enhanced interactions between electrons and light. For instance, because light can be rapidly modulated at the femtosecond timescale, PINEM represents an ideal way to induce an ultrafast phase and/or amplitude change on the electron wave function. This is the key concept behind a new exciting paradigm for electron engineering, i.e. a special form of electron-beam shaping mediated by light: at its heart is the interaction between the microscope's electron pulse and a properly-designed time-varying electromagnetic field. Achieving this form of ultrafast modulation of the electron is challenging because the electron wave and the modulating photon wave need to be not only carefully timed, but also sufficiently coherent, i.e. well shaped in space. On the other hand, this opens new exciting routes for the dynamical investigation of matter, endowing scientists with new superpowers to probe quantities of interest with unprecedented sensitivities.

The first steps in this line of research have been taken by the scientists involved in the SMART-electron project, who have experimentally demonstrated spatio-temporal shaping of a free-electron wave function using light. In particular, they showed the quantised light-induced modulation of electron states in their

energy-momentum phase space, as well as attosecond electron modulation, and orbital angular momentum transfer from photons to electrons. In the latter experiment, they showed for the first time the generation and sub-femtosecond control of ultrashort electron vortex beams, which is crucial, for instance, for the dynamic investigation of magnetic nanomaterials.

These experiments can be viewed as the first examples of a more general concept, whereby an electron beam is shaped arbitrarily by an appropriate electromagnetic field due to a light beam. This is one of the main concepts of the EU-funded FET-Open project SMART-electron, which aims to create a photonic-based free-electron modulator for dynamic electron phase manipulation.

The main concepts behind SE

The wave nature of light has enabled the development of several tools to shape it into new wave structures characterised by non-trivial spatio-temporal properties. Beyond traditional lenses, spatial light modulators (SLM) and metamaterials have revolutionized optics by enabling efficient control of electromagnetic fields in new and unexpected ways, leading to significant impact in both fundamental and applied science such as the development of super-resolved optical microscopies.

The vision behind the SMART-electron project is to establish a novel technological paradigm that exploits the power of control reached with light to coherently shape electron matter waves, revolutionizing the way materials are investigated in electron microscopy. This will grant us access into new phenomena benefiting from interaction with the electron charge and with a spatial accuracy at least three orders of magnitude better than what is currently achievable in light optics.

Spatial and temporal shaping of electron beams could provide new routes toward image-resolution enhancement, selective probing, low-dose imaging, faster acquisition, depth information, and high temporal and energetic resolutions.

Going beyond current paradigms

Reaching this new vision requires, however, a radical departure from current electron microscopy schemes, which so far rely on passive static modulation of the electron wave function using monolithic phase masks, such as spiral plates and holograms, or slowly-varying electrostatic and magnetostatic displays (milliseconds or longer).

In SMART-electron, we will pursue a disruptive approach for coherent and arbitrary dynamical shaping of the electron wave properties down to the femtosecond range and below, many orders of magnitude faster than conventional schemes.

This will open new frontiers not only in microscopy but also in optoelectronics, quantum information and biosensing. To reach the required high speed, flexibility and precise phase control needed to make such potential a reality, we introduce a new paradigm where properly synthesized ultrafast light fields will be used for engineering the electron phase space.

SE technological breakthrough

SMART-electron aims at developing an innovative technological platform for designing, realizing and operating all-optical rapidly-programmable phase masks for electrons.

These would rely on a light-mediated coherent modulation of the longitudinal and transverse phase of an electron wave function, exploiting the strong interaction between free electrons and optical fields in illuminated nanostructures.

The fast, arbitrary, and versatile control achievable with such ultrafast light fields would allow us to dynamically manipulate the spatial, temporal, energetic, and momentum distributions of an electron in a coherent and correlated manner. The main idea is that a simultaneous time-varying and spatially-varying phase modulation, as induced by quantized energy-momentum exchanges between the electron and the driving optical field, will lead to significant non-conservative forces that result in a strong modification of the electron group velocity profile.

The extremely fast control and the highly versatile manipulation, together with the ability to couple longitudinal and transverse phase shaping, are unattainable features with existing monolithic phase masks or electrostatic displays, allowing us to access a completely unexplored range of the phase space. This is what makes our Photonic-based free-Electron Modulators (PELMs) unique with respect to current schemes. SMART-electron has a clear technological outcome and a powerful strategic objective. The technological outcome is, as mentioned above, the development of a photonic modulator for dynamic multidimensional control of electrons. To carry out this objective, we will use advanced theoretical and experimental methods enabling precise modelling, design, and characterization of the light-induced electron phase shaping. This will be instrumental to the following design and practical realization of such photonic modulators.

SE strategic objectives

The strategic objective of SMART-electron will be the ability to radically change how materials are investigated in electron microscopy, in particular leading to unprecedented visualization of entangled states in quantum systems, real-time electrochemical reactions, and biomimetic nanoparticles in cells for drug delivery.

To achieve this objective, we will implement three new beyond-the-state-of-the-art electron imaging techniques enabled by such superior electron phase control. The first one is a Ramsey-type Holographic Imaging for disentangling the contribution of hybridized low-energy modes in strongly-correlated systems, which is a long-standing issue of key importance for their technological implementation. The second one is an Electron Single-Pixel Imaging method that has been only recently proposed for optical detection and now, using PELMs, would become possible also in electron microscopy. This will permit lower electron doses, faster acquisition rates and more reliable 3D imaging of nanoscopic objects in their natural environment, which are key features for the investigation of transport of Lithium ions during a battery operation. The third one is a Quantum Cathodoluminescence scheme based on an enhanced light emission when materials are interrogated with structured free-electron waves, allowing unprecedented spatio-temporal localization of nanoparticles in cells for drug delivery and nanomedicine applications.

By boldly surpassing the current paradigms of electron manipulation, the project, which is feasible yet groundbreaking, has the potential to drive electron microscopy into a new and exciting age where scientists will benefit from new tools with unprecedented performances that were unimaginable until now.

Introductory bibliography

Ultrafast Electron Microscopy

1. A.H. Zewail, Science 328, 187-193 (2010)
2. L Piazza, DJ Masiel, T LaGrange, BW Reed, B Barwick, F. Carbone, Journal Chemical Physics 423, 79-84 (2013)
3. G.M. Vanacore, A.W.P. Fitzpatrick, A.H. Zewail, Nano Today 11, 228 (2016)

Photon Induced Near Field Electron Microscopy

4. B. Barwick, D.J. Flannigan, A.H. Zewail, Nature 462, 902 (2009)
5. S.T. Park, M. Lin, A.H. Zewail, New J. Phys. 12, 123028 (2010)
6. F.J. Garcia De Abajo, A. Asenjo-Garcia, M. Kociak, Nano Lett. 10, 1859 (2010)
7. D.J. Flannigan, B. Barwick, A.H. Zewail, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA 107, 9933 (2010)
8. A. Yurtsever, R.M. van der Veen, A.H. Zewail, Science 335, 59 (2012)
9. L. Piazza, T.T.A. Lummen, E. Quiñonez, Y. Murooka, B.W. Reed, B. Barwick, F. Carbone, Nat. Commun. 6, 6407 (2015)
10. A. Feist, K.E. Echternkamp, J. Schauss, S.V. Yalunin, S. Schäfer, C. Ropers, Nature 521, 200 (2015)
11. E. Pomarico, I. Madan, G. Berruto, G.M. Vanacore, K. Wang, I. Kaminer, F.J. García de Abajo, F. Carbone, ACS Photonics 5, 759 (2018)
12. X. Fu, F. Barantani, S. Gargiulo, I. Madan, G. Berruto, T. Lagrange, L. Jin, J. Wu, G.M. Vanacore, F. Carbone, Y. Zhu, Nat. Commun. 11, 5770 (2020)

Light-induced phase shaping of a free-electron wave function

13. I. Madan, G.M. Vanacore, S. Gargiulo, T. LaGrange, F. Carbone, Appl. Phys. Lett. 116, 230502 (2020)
14. G. M. Vanacore, I. Madan, F. Carbone, La Rivista del Nuovo Cimento, 43, 567–597 (2020)
15. O. Reinhardt, I. Kaminer, ACS Photonics 7, 2859 (2020)

Attosecond coherent control

16. K.E. Priebe, C. Rathje, S.V. Yalunin, T. Hohage, A. Feist, S. Schäfer, C. Ropers, Nat. Photonics 11, 793 (2017)
17. M. Kozák, J. McNeur, K.J. Leedle, H. Deng, N. Schönenberger, A. Ruehl, I. Hartl, J.S. Harris, R.L. Byer, P. Hommelhoff, Nat. Commun. 8, 14342 (2017)
18. Y. Morimoto, P. Baum, Nat. Phys. 14, 252 (2018)

20. G.M. Vanacore, I. Madan, G. Berruto, K. Wang, E. Pomarico, R.J. Lamb, D. McGrouther, I. Kaminer, B. Barwick, F.J. García de Abajo, F. Carbone, Nat. Commun. 9, 2694 (2018)

21. N. Schönenberger, A. Mittelbach, P. Yousefi, J. McNeur, U. Niedermayer, and P. Hommelhoff Phys. Rev. Lett. 123, 264803 (2019)

22. Y. Morimoto, P. Baum, Phys. Rev. Lett. 125, 193202 (2020)

- ***Ramsey control and Ramsey-like holography***

23. K.E. Echternkamp, A. Feist, S. Schäfer, C. Ropers, Nat. Phys. 12, 1000 (2016)

24. I. Madan, G.M. Vanacore, E. Pomarico, G. Berruto, R.J. Lamb, D. McGrouther, T.T.A. Lummen, T. Latychevskaia, F.J. García de Abajo, F. Carbone, Sci. Adv. 5, eaav8358 (2019)

- ***Strong coupling regime and cavity QED***

25. O. Kfir, Phys. Rev. Lett. 123, 103602 (2019)

26. V. Di Giulio, M. Kociak, F.J.G. de Abajo, Optica 6, 1524 (2019)

27. O. Kfir, H. Lourenço-Martins, G. Storeck, M. Sivilis, T.R. Harvey, T.J. Kippenberg, A. Feist, C. Ropers, Nature 582, 46 (2020)

28. K. Wang, R. Dahan, M. Shentcic, Y. Kauffmann, A.B. Hayun, O. Reinhardt, S. Tsesses, I. Kaminer, Nature 582, 50 (2020)

29. R. Dahan, S. Nehemia, M. Shentcic, O. Reinhardt, Y. Adiv, X. Shi, O. Be'er, M. H. Lynch, Y. Kurman, K. Wang & I. Kaminer, Nature Physics 16, 1123–1131 (2020)

- ***Linear momentum modulation***

30. Y. Morimoto, P. Baum, Nat. Phys. 14, 252 (2018)

31. G.M. Vanacore, I. Madan, G. Berruto, K. Wang, E. Pomarico, R.J. Lamb, D. McGrouther, I. Kaminer, B. Barwick, F.J. García de Abajo, F. Carbone, Nat. Commun. 9, 2694 (2018)

32. C. Kealhofer, W. Schneider, D. Ehberger, A. Ryabov, F. Krausz, P. Baum, Science 352, 429 (2016)

33. M. Kozák, J. McNeur, K.J. Leedle, H. Deng, N. Schönenberger, A. Ruehl, I. Hartl, J.S. Harris, R.L. Byer, P. Hommelhoff, Nat. Commun. 8, 14342 (2017)

34. D. Ehberger, K.J. Mohler, T. Vasileiadis, R. Ernstorfer, L. Waldecker, P. Baum, Phys. Rev. Appl. 11, 024034 (2019)

35. A. Feist, S.V. Yalunin, S. Schafer, C. Ropers, Phys. Rev. Res. 2, 043227 (2020)

36. F.J. García de Abajo, B. Barwick, F. Carbone, Phys. Rev. B 94, 041404 (2016)

37. N. Talebi, C. Lienau, New J. Phys. 21, 093016 (2019)

- ***Vortex phase shaping and transverse modulation***

38. G.M. Vanacore, G. Berruto, I. Madan, E. Pomarico, P. Biagioni, R.J. Lamb, D. McGrouther, O. Reinhardt, I. Kaminer, B. Barwick, H. Larocque, V. Grillo, E. Karimi, F.J. García de Abajo, F. Carbone, Nat. Mater. 18, 573 (2019)

39. J. Handali, P. Shakya, B. Barwick, Opt. Express 23, 5236 (2015)

40. W. Cai, O. Reinhardt, I. Kaminer, F.J.G. De Abajo, Phys. Rev. B 98, 45424 (2018)

41. O. Schwartz, J.J. Axelrod, S.L. Campbell, C. Turnbaugh, R.M. Glaeser, H. Müller, Nat. Methods 16, 1016 (2019)

42. A. Konečná, F.J.G. de Abajo, Phys. Rev. Lett. 125, 030801 (2020)

43. F. Javier García de Abajo, A. Konečná, Phys. Rev. Lett. 126, 123901 (2021)

Research papers

Andrea Konečná, Enzo Rotunno, Vincenzo Grillo, F. Javier Garcia de Abajo, Giovanni Maria Vanacore

Single-Pixel Imaging in Space and Time with Optically-Modulated Free Electrons

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.07332> (2022)

Akhil Kallepalli, Lorenzo Viani, Daan Stellinga, Enzo Rotunno, Ming-Jie Sun, Richard Bowman, Paolo Rosi, Stefano Frabboni, Roberto Balboni, Andrea Migliori, Vincenzo Grillo, Miles Padgett

Computational ghost imaging for transmission electron microscopy

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2204.09997> (2022)

Shai Tseses, Raphael Dahan, Kangpeng Wang, Ori Reinhardt, Guy Bartal, Ido Kaminer

Tunable photon-induced spatial modulation of free electrons

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.08518> (2022)

Yadong Han, Junhong Yu, Hang Zhang, Fang Xu, Kunlin Peng, Xiaoyuan Zhou, Liang Qiao, Oleg V Misochko, Kazutaka G Nakamura, Giovanni M Vanacore, Jianbo Hu

Photoinduced Ultrafast Symmetry Switch in SnSe

Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters 13, 442-448 (2022)

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2107.01576>

Jianbo Hu, Yang Xiang, Beatrice Matilde Ferrari, Giovanni Maria Vanacore

Mode-selective exciton-phonon dynamics in MoS₂

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.15240> (2021)

E. Rotunno, S. Gargiulo, G. M. Vanacore, C. Mechel, A. Tavabi, R.E. Dunin Borkowski, F. Carbone, I.Maidan, M. Zanfrognini, S. Frabboni, T. Guner, E. Karimi, I. Kaminer, V. Grillo

One-dimensional ghost imaging with an electron microscope: a route towards ghost imaging with inelastically scattered electrons

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.08955> (2021)

EU FUNDED

SMART-electron has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 964591.

The European Commission is the executive body of the European Union. Its tasks include implementing decisions and managing the day-to-day business of the EU (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Commission), as well as the implementation of the EU budget. As part of its remit, the EC directly funds trans-national scientific research projects through dedicated calls for entries, such as those of the FET Programme.

We would like to thank the European Union for making our project (along with similar projects) possible. We recognise their important function in promoting the advancement of knowledge and in helping to establish fruitful international long-term relationships involving institutions and companies. We believe that these efforts help us all to better understand and appreciate our cultural diversity.

EVENTS

2022 Nano Colloquia: Artificial neural network for automatic alignment of electron optical devices

Speaker: Enzo Rotunno

Affiliation: Cnr Nano S3

Date 2022-03-03

Time: 15:00

Venue: <https://global.gotomeeting.com/join/241151485>

Host: Massimo Rontani

See the [Slides](#) of the presentation.

Seminar realized in the framework of the funded project: SMART-electron H2020-FET Open Grant n. 964591

One of the most significant developments in the recent history of electron microscopy is beam shaping. Through electron optical components, based on microelectromechanical systems technology, it is possible to generate vortex beams [1], non-diffracting beams [2], compact aberration correctors [3] and quantum state analysers [4].

Although the basic concept of the operation of each lens and optical element is known, the overall behaviour of the microscope is not predictable in detail and the quality of microscope performance is limited by the skill of the user.

Recent years have seen the exponential growth of Artificial Intelligence (AI) which have clearly demonstrated their ability to control a variety of complex systems ranging from large industrial machines, through vehicles, to small appliances in our homes.

We make use of artificial neural networks (ANN) [5], a class of AIs able to autonomously learn from a large set of training examples, how to govern electron optical devices within a transmission electron microscope.

We are motivated by the specific case of an orbital angular momentum (OAM) sorter [6], which makes use of electron beam shaping to measure an electron beam's component of OAM in the propagation direction.

After the training, the CNN is capable of correctly identify the microscope configuration (parameters like defocus, misalignments and the excitation of the OAM sorter) from a single spectrum image and to suggest the corrections required to reach ideal resolution.

The proposed method is not however limited to the OAM sorter. Such an approach can be applied in real time to align other complex experimental apparatus, based on minimal experimental data. We envisage that in the future experimental devices will be able to self-diagnose and communicate with operators in real-time.

[1] A. H. Tavabi, et al. Phys. Rev. Research, 2 (2020), 013185.

[2] V. Grillo, et al. Phys. Rev. X, 4 (2014), 011013.

[3] V. Grillo et al. Opt. Express, 25 (2017), 21851.

[4] A.H. Tavabi et al. arXiv: 1910.03706.

[5] K. Simonyan, et al. arXiv: 1409.1556v6.

[6] M. Weigert, et al. Nat. Methods, 15 (2018), 1090–1097.

2022 SMART-electron Wikipedia Edit-a-thon

The webinar, which will last 3 hours, will be held on:

5 April 2022, 14:00 CET

You can register here:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/82859116924?pwd=SFJieE8yVlI0VzE5c2VwTTItKy9Ydz09>

More info here:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Edit-a-thon/SMARTelectron_Wikipedia_Edit-a-thon_2022

We look forward to seeing you!

The SMART-electron community has mobilised in order to launch an online Wikipedia Edit-a-thon Extravaganza of scientific article writing. The objective is to broaden the scope and the number of articles in the free encyclopaedia.

SMART-electron actively supports initiatives that aim to improve online accessibility to scientific knowledge. By participating in this initiative you will be able to contribute personally, from your home, to this effort to make science more easily accessible to everyone.

The Edit-a-thon will place a special emphasis on science and especially Physics articles. It will not be limited only to Wikipedia – for instance participants will be able to upload images to Wikimedia Commons.

The Edit-a-thon will begin with a short introductory webinar, held on Zoom, by Wikipedian Alessandro Marchetti. By the end of it, participants will be able to start contributing to Wikipedia.

2021 International Conference

1-3 September 2021

Science and applications of coherent electron beam manipulation

This conference, jointly organised by the SMART-electron, Q-SORT, 3D MAGiC, Holo Workshop, MINEON projects, explores coherent electron-beam manipulation from different, complementary perspectives.

Any COVID-19 restriction at the time of the conference will be dealt with by holding some or all of the talks online.

Concepts such as electron coherence, electron phase control & holography, characterisation of magnetic phase, light-electron interaction, phase plates for imaging or for beam shaping, are all at the forefront of electron microscopy research. Moreover, they are also of interest outside the microscopy field.

In this joint conference, we will explore some of these themes together: cross-fertilisation and topic contiguity will stimulate discussions and new ideas. The conference also aims to facilitate networking, fostering an even larger community. The different reference communities of the four organising projects will have the chance to speak to each other.

The themes at the centre of this conference affect the design of electron-based measurement instruments such as the electron microscope and in general of all electron optics. Not only can we measure the electron phase and through it the electric and magnetic fields, but we can also control it, tune the phase of light waves interacting with the electron beam, as well as the kind of electron interaction with the sample — all of this while controlling the state (e.g. the magnetisation) of the sample itself.

The events are all happening online, but preference is given to round tables and discussions, so as to keep things lively and engaging.

The conference is structured around three sessions, pertaining to Q-SORT & SMART-electron, 3D MAGiC, and Holo respectively.

The Q-SORT + SMART-electron session will regard topics such as electron beam shaping, its applications in spectroscopies, electron light interaction, and time-resolved phase-coherent experiments.

The 3D MAGiC session will focus more on the new ideas of control and measurement of surprising magnetic states with unconventional and advanced magnetic field control.

The Holo session will regard the more general field of holography, with emphasis on new ideas for measuring fields, measuring coherence, reconstructing the electron phase, improving the SNR through phase shifting or stack acquisition, and their applications in material science.

[Download the Programme](#)

[Register](#)

[Access the event](#)

Joint Q-Sort and SMARTelectron Session

Recent developments in the spatial and temporal shaping of electron beams are spreading rapidly, as they provide routes towards image-resolution enhancement and novel microscopy techniques. Most of these methods, such as passive and dynamic wave-packet modulation, as well as structured light-matter interaction, are inspired by their optical counterpart and have now been explored in transmission electron microscopy. However, other schemes exist, inspired by quantum optics, such as the so-called “interaction-free” methods, optimal quantum state tomography, and ghost imaging, which may be implemented in electron microscopy. These new methods hold the promise of new measurements at different space-time scales, allowing the verification of new quantum phenomena and their interpretations, as well as the optimisation of experiments so as to extract new quantities and new dynamical descriptions of matter. This session aims to gather experts from the fields of electron and laser beam shaping, methodological cryomicroscopy, free-space electron optics and related sub-fields of quantum mechanics. Reaching the end of the Q-SORT project, it is the right moment to consider what is the state of the art and what is the future of these ideas in many directions as witnessed by new projects and ideas. It will therefore be a new opportunity for the participants to foresee together the most important directions that electron optics is taking in the quantum microscopy direction. This session will also examine technological applications of beam shaping techniques, with particular reference to MINEON, the EIC Innovation Launchpad project which constitutes the continuation of Q-SORT.

3D Magic Session

The 3D MAGiC ERC SYNERGY project studies three-dimensional magnetic solitons. This session brings together experts on magnetic imaging, magnetic manipulation, theory and device applications. The aim of 3D MAGiC is to study still largely unknown nanoscale magnetic structures that have particle-like properties and whose existence has so far only been predicted theoretically. Novel theoretical and experimental approaches in this area will be discussed. These include methods based on electron-matter and light-matter interactions, to measure and characterise magnetic fields with high temporal and spatial resolution. This session of the conference aims to stimulate synergies and the interest of this project in the field of coherent-electron based characterisation of magnetism and especially holography and ultrafast pump-and-probe measurements.

Holography Workshop

The Holography workshop aims to be an informal session that inspires discussion about all the different types of electron holography, whether it be inline, off-axis, or dark-field electron holography. The general themes encompass all the practical aspects involved from electron beam and biprism parameters, image acquisition, post processing, to phase analysis. These will include some common practice techniques, but placing emphasis on new ideas for measuring electromagnetic fields, analysis of coherence, reconstructing the electron phase, improving the SNR through phase shifting or stack acquisition, double exposure, pushing the limits of spatial resolution and phase sensitivity, holographic vector field electron tomography, image alignment and their applications in material science and a range of practical fields. The scope of this session will also cover other electron microscopy methods directly related to the handling, measuring and controlling the phase of the electron wave. Indeed, recent advances in ptychography, iDPC and 4D STEM are of great importance and relevant to this session, with fruitful discussions about the combined use of such techniques to solve problems, are strongly encouraged, as well as any challenges that are involved. The session will include several invited speakers that are experts in electron holography and other phase-related techniques, but all participants will be able to share their latest ideas and discoveries through relaxed dialogues.

2021 CNR-NANO: FIM-S3 Seminar

FIM-S3 SEMINAR

Prof Giovanni Maria Vanacore

Date and Time:

Wednesday May 26th, 15:30 (SHARP)

Google Meet:

<https://meet.google.com/gax-mddz-jzq>

Speaker:

Prof Giovanni Maria Vanacore – University of Milano Bicocca

Title:

Ultrafast coherent manipulation of a free-electron wave function via electron-light quantum interaction

The interaction between light and electrons can be exploited for generating radiation, such as in synchrotrons and FEL, or for controlling electron beams for dynamical investigation of materials. Using electromagnetic fields, the coherent control of an electron wave function can be pushed to unexplored timescales, enabling new applications in light-assisted quantum devices and diagnostics at extremely small timescales.

In this contribution, I will describe an innovative method for coherent longitudinal and transverse phase manipulation of a free-electron wave function. Using appropriately synthesized light fields I will demonstrate how to modulate the energy, linear momentum and orbital angular momentum (vorticity) of the electron wave function with sub-fs precision [1-3]. The experiments have been performed in an ultrafast-TEM, where a relativistic pulsed electron beam was made to interact with properly shaped near-field. The energy-momentum exchange resulting from such interaction was directly mapped via momentum-resolved ultrafast electron energy-loss spectroscopy.

Our approach for longitudinal and transverse electron phase modulation at the sub-fs timescale would pave the way to achieve unprecedented insights into non-equilibrium phenomena in advanced quantum materials [4], playing a decisive role in the rational design and engineering of future photonics and electronics applications [5].

[1] G. M. Vanacore et al., Nature Communication 9, 2694 (2018).

[2] G. M. Vanacore et al., Nature Materials 18, 573-579 (2019).

[3] I. Madan*, G. M. Vanacore* et al., Science Advances 5, eaav8358 (2019).

[4] I. Madan*, G. M. Vanacore* et al., Appl. Phys. Lett. 116, 230502 (2020).

[5] G. M. Vanacore et al., La Rivista del Nuovo Cimento 43, 567–597(2020).

Host: Marco Gibertini (FIM, UNIMORE) and Claudia Cardoso (S3, CNR-NANO)

2021 Smart-Electron Prizes at the Wiki Science Competition

The Wiki Science Competition (WSC) is an international photo contest for the sciences. It is organised by Wikimedia, that is the movement behind [Wikipedia](https://www.wikipedia.org/), the free encyclopaedia – a global collaboration authored by volunteers.

The WSC was brought to life to encourage the creation and, especially, the free sharing of all sorts of imagery about the sciences. It takes place once every two years in November.

The WSC happens at two levels: national and international. It means that in many countries there will be a national contest with its own jury and prizes (more from [here](#)). Winning pictures will advance to the international final, and will be judged by the [international jury](#) to chose the overall winners. For countries where there is no national organising team, a second international jury will take their place and chose the

national candidates for the international final: the goal is that all the photographers in the world have the possibility to participate in the competition.

Any form of support is welcome: from uploading a single image, or spreading the word about the contest, to becoming a partner or sponsor.

The Wiki Science Competition officially announced a new international sponsor for the 2021 edition: SMART-electron.

SMART-electron offers ****2**** special Prizes for the best image within the Wiki Science Competition contest: one for the best image in the special category “Women in Science” and the other for the best image in the existing category “Microscopy images” .

The two Special SMART-electron Prizes for the Wiki Science Competition seek to promote excellence in image craft and aim to leverage the appeal of high-impact imagery to further the visibility of both SMART-electron and Wikipedia.

The photos will be selected among all national finalists. In order to help evaluate all the entries, one person from the SMART-electron consortium (Dr. Giovanni Maria Vanacore) also joined the 2021 international jury.

SMARTelectron has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 964591.

SMART-electron, Q-SORT, MINEON and MAX at the Researcher’s Night 2021

We’re ready! CnrNano responds to the call from the European Commission regarding the Researchers’ Night, which this year will take place in 29 countries on Friday 24 September 2021. The European Researchers’ Night is a Europe-wide public event, which displays the diversity of science and its impact on citizens’ daily lives in fun, inspiring ways.

Both units of CnrNano will join the event, contributing to the local initiatives in the city center of Modena and Pisa with presentations and demonstrations, thanks to a number of researchers passionate about outreach.

In Modena [“Disegnare il futuro dell’elettronica”](#) (via San Geminiano 3, h. 20.00 – 23.00): Claudia Cardoso and Vincenzo Grillo, together with Marco Gibertini from Unimore, will tackle a presentation and a playful experiment dedicated to bidimensional materials, their unique properties and their potential for future electronics.

In Pisa, [“Il nanomondo dentro di noi”](#) (Largo Ciro Menotti, h 16.00 – 22.00): research groups of Ilaria Tonazzini and of Luana Persano will show how thanks to nanotechnology they can imagine and develop innovative tools for medicine and health, from miniaturized lab-on-chips to release drugs into the brain to implantable devices to improve vital functions.

For our researchers and the whole CnrNano institute the European Researchers’ Night is a unique opportunity to engage with citizens of all ages to raise awareness about our research and its impact on society.

The event in Modena is organised within the Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia Researchers’ Night and in collaboration with the following projects, funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme:

Q-SORT Grant Agreement no. 766970,

MINEON Grant Agreement no. 101035013,

SMART-electron Grant Agreement no. 964591,

MaX Grant Agreement no. 824143.

The event in Pisa is organised within the initiative Bright-Night Toscana and will be attended by a researcher recruited under the MSCA-IF grant BIOIMD (G.A. n. 896811)

PRESS ROOM & DOWNLOADS

For all press/media needs please refer to the downloadable material below or email us at qsortpress@qedproductions.co.uk

Our team is here to respond to all media enquiries about SMART-electron.

Press release

Press photos

Logo

Graphic design standard manual & Package

Poster / Rollup / Brochure / Tote-bag Package

CONTACTS

Project Coordinator
Giovanni Maria Vanacore
giovanni.vanacore@unimib.it

Communication Manager
Luca Marco Carlo Giberti
lmcg@qedproductions.co.uk

% Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca
Piazza dell'Ateneo Nuovo, 1 - 20126, Milano
Tel. 02 6448 1

NEWS

Radio interview at SMART-CITY on Radio 24

<https://www.radio24.ilsole24ore.com/programmi/smart-city/puntata/smart-electron-via-progetto-che-vuol-mettere-occhiali-microscopio-elettronico-205020-ADqCA1MB>

A new EU-funded H2020 project promises to revolutionize electron microscopy

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/a-new-eu-funded-h2020-project-promises-to-revolutionize-electron-microscopy/>

FIM3- Seminar

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/cnr-nano-fim-s3-seminar/>

Super scientists invited to nano innovation 2021 forum

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/smart-electron-news-is-a-continuous-flow-of-articles-links-and-events-stay-tuned-with-smart-electron/>

Nano Colloquia 2022: Artificial neural network for automatic alignment of electron optical devices

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/nano-colloquia-2022-artificial-neural-network-for-automatic-alignment-of-electron-optical-devices/>

SMART-electron Wikipedia Edit-a-thon 2022

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/smart-electron-wikipedia-edit-a-thon-2022/>

The Smart-Electron Prizes at the Wiki Science Competition 2021

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/the-smart-electron-prizes-at-the-wiki-science-competition-2021>

SMART-electron at the Researchers' Night 2021

<https://www.smartelectron.eu/researchers-night/>

ANNEX 3: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	ITALY	UNIMIB
2 ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE EPFL	SWITZERLAND	EPFL
3 FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES	SPAIN	ICFO
4 TECHNION - ISRAEL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	ISRAEL	TECHNION
5 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
6 HOLOEYE PHOTONICS AG	GERMANY	HOLOEYE
7 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UK	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL